

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES OPEN UNIVERSITY

MASTER OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

RAUL B. GACUTAN

**THE CAMPAIGN STRATEGY OF THE MARITIME POLICE AGAINST ILLEGAL
FISHING IN BALAYAN BAY**

Special Problem Adviser:

ANTHEA V. MARIANO

Faculty of Management and Development Studies

01 December 2023

Permission is given for the following people to have access to this Special Problem, subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy, and any contractual obligations:

Invention (I)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Publication (P)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Confidential (C)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Free (F)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or	<input type="checkbox"/> No

Student's signature:

SP adviser's signature:

University Permission Page

THE CAMPAIGN STRATEGY OF THE MARITIME POLICE AGAINST ILLEGAL FISHING AT BALAYAN BAY

I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this Academic Work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy, and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page.

I specifically allow the University to:

- a. Upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/school/institute/department and any other databases available on the public internet;
- b. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and
- c. Give open access to the work, thus allowing “fair use” of the work in accordance with the provision of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly, and research purposes.

Raul B. Gacutan / 07/28/23

Signature over Student Name and Date

Acceptance Page:

This Special Project titled: “**The Campaign Strategy of the Maritime Police against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management.

ANTHEA V. MARIANO
Faculty-in-charge, ENRM 290 (Special Problem)

31 July 2023

(Date)

CONSUELO DL. HABITO
Program Chair

29 November 2023

(Date)

JOANE V. SERRANO
Dean

Faculty of Management and Development Studies

01 December 2023
(Date)

DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface.
- II. Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used.
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

Raul B. Gacutan

Acknowledgment

The author expresses his sincere gratitude and appreciation to all who have unselfishly helped the researcher to make the writing of this thesis possible.

First to the Almighty, our Creator and constant shield and mighty fortress in hurdling the daily challenges in the life of our Lord Jesus;

To the Chief of Regional Maritime Unit 4, Police Colonel Greg Togonon for his generous assistance during the conduct of research; To Governor Hermilando Mandanas of Batangas and all the mayors of the coastal municipalities of Batangas at Balayan Bay.

To all my professors of the University of the Philippines Open University headed by Dr. Joane V. Serrano, Dean of the Faculty of Management and Development Studies (FMDS) for providing the researcher with proper guidance and opportunities to pursue his career goals.

To the Station Chief of Batangas Maritime Police Station, Police Captain Benito Siddayao, and his personnel for responding to the inquiries made by the researcher and for their invaluable support;

The researcher is especially grateful to Dr. Consuelo Habito, Program Chair, Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management, as a member of the panel on oral examination for generously sharing her insights and expertise and for guiding the researcher in his research journey;

To Anthea Mariano, his Faculty-In-Charge, for all the inputs, guidance, and support he provided the author to make this Special Problem a quality output; and

And finally, to his beloved family, his wife Rosario, his son Ralph Ian, and his daughter Rose Eunice, for their moral support and source of inspiration.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Declaration	iv
Acknowledgments	v
Table of Contents	vi
List of Figures	vii
List of Tables	viii
List of Appendices	x
ABSTRACT	xi
I. INTRODUCTION	16
II. RELATED LITERATURE	21
III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY	49
IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY	50
V. RATIONALE	52
VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS	60
VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY	61
VIII. METHODOLOGY	68
IX. RESULTS, ANALYSIS, AND DISCUSSION	75
X. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION	107
XI. REFERENCES	115

List of Figures

Figure 1	Conceptual framework on the Partnership of the Maritime Police and Bantay Dagat against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay	57
Figure 2	Map of Balayan Bay showing the intrusion of fishing vessels coming from other provinces to commit illegal fishing	61
Figure 3	Graphical representation of the increasing trend of illegal fishing in Balayan Bay from CY 2017-2021	66

List of Tables

Table 1	Breakdown of the Number of Incidents of Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay	62
Table 2	Status of Prosecution of Reported Illegal Fishing Activities at Balayan Bay	63
Table 3	Common Profile of Illegal Fishing Violators at Balayan Bay	65
Table 4	Respondents of the Study	70
Table 5	Respondents' Assessment of the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and <i>Bantay Dagat</i> Against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Innovative Approach	77
Table 6	Respondents' Assessment of the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and <i>Bantay Dagat</i> Against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Application of Human Resources	80
Table 7	Respondents' Assessment of the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and <i>Bantay Dagat</i> Against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Coordinated Activities	82
Table 8	Summary Assessment on the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and <i>Bantay Dagat</i> against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay	84
Table 9	Problems Encountered by the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and <i>Bantay Dagat</i> Against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Innovative Approach	87
Table 10	Problems Encountered by the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and <i>Bantay Dagat</i> Against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Application of Human Resources	89
Table 11	Problems Encountered by the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and <i>Bantay Dagat</i> Against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Coordinated Activities	91
Table 12	Summary Assessment on the Problem Encountered by the Partnership against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay	93
Table 13	Proposed Measures to Enhance the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and <i>Bantay Dagat</i> Against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Innovative Approach	95
Table 14	Proposed Measures to Enhance the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and <i>Bantay Dagat</i> Against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Application of Human Resources	97

Table 15	Proposed Measures to Enhance the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and <i>Bantay Dagat</i> Against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Coordinated Activities	99
Table 16	Summary Assessment of the Proposed Measures to Enhance the Partnership against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay	101

List of Appendices

1	Survey Questionnaires	118
2	Pictorial During Interview with Dr. Rogelio Demelletes	127
3	Pictorial During Interview with Police Colonel Greg Togonon	128
4	Pictorial During Interview with Police Captain Benito Siddayao Jr.	129
5	Pictorial During Interview with Engineer Ian Manalo	130
6	Pictorial During the Distribution of Survey Questionnaires with Maritime Police	131
7	Pictorial During the Distribution of Survey Questionnaires to the Bantay Dagat of Lemery, Batangas.	132
8	Pictorial During the Distribution of Survey Questionnaires with the Residents of coastal Barangays of Mabini, Batangas.	133
9	Pictorial During the Distribution of Survey Questionnaires to the Residents of Coastal Barangays at Balayan, Batangas.	134
10	Pictorial During the Distribution of Survey Questionnaires with the Residents of Coastal Barangays at San Luis, Batangas.	135
11	Pictorial during meeting with representatives from BFAR, FARMC, and Bantay Dagat to discuss their strategies against illegal fishing.	136

Abstract

The Campaign Strategy of the Maritime Police Against Illegal Fishing at Balayan Bay

The Problem

The specific problems in the study included 1. The assessment of the partnership of the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay in the areas of; Innovative Approach; Application of Human Resources; and Coordinated Activities; 2. The identification of the common problems encountered by the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay as regards the Innovative Approach; Application of Human Resources; and Coordinated Activities; 3. The measures proposed to address the problems in the partnership relative to the afore-cited variables.

Research Methodology

The study was basically descriptive and specifically of a descriptive-analytical nature. It gathered data from representative portions of the respondents- the Maritime Police, the *Bantay Dagat*, and residents in the coastal barangays of Balayan Bay. It drew accomplished survey questionnaires from the selected samples of respondents. The sample size was determined using the Slovincs formula with a five percent (5%) margin of error. The respondents in the sample were selected using the stratified sampling technique.

Findings

The findings revealed the following. 1) The three groups of respondents assessed the partnership of the Maritime Police and Bantay Dagat as “Evident” with an Overall Weighted Mean (OWM) of 3.83 in terms of Innovative Approach, Application of Human Resources, and Coordinative Activities. 2) The three groups of respondents have indicated various degrees of seriousness on the lack of training as an apparent problem encountered by the partnership in these areas, however, the three groups, in general, addressed the problem as “Moderately Serious”, with an OWM of 2.73. 3) The summary evaluation of the proposed measures needed to address the problems encountered by the Partnership obtained an OWM of 4.07 which is verbally interpreted as Recommended through conducting joint training of the Maritime Police and Bantay Daga to enhance their law enforcement capabilities. 4) The results of the interviews conducted all pointed to the positive assessment and acceptance of the partnership of the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* against the campaign against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay. Moreover, all sectors underscored the need to enhance the partnership to ensure work efficiency in the implementation of the campaign against illegal fishing. Financial and logistical supports were major considerations that must be balanced with efficient and appropriate training.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were derived: 1) The partnership of the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* in Balayan Bay is evident and therefore, felt and valued by various sectors of the communities; 2) Based on the survey, the enhancement of the partnership of the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* in Balayan Bay can be done through the conduct of training which is a highly

recommended measure to improve law enforcement operations. The following activities stood out as priorities; “Monthly conduct of *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan* to serve as a gauge of community awareness on the bad effects of illegal fishing”; and Conduct of quarterly Coastal Law Enforcement Training of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat*; and 3) A regular conduct of Monthly or Quarterly *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan* with the participation of community residents to be presided over by the representatives of the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat*.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are forwarded:

1. The partnership must stress the growing need for stronger enforcement of the fishery law. However, this can only be achieved if the expected outputs are balanced by the required training that must be conducted. The formulation of Coastal Law Enforcement Training (CLET) must be done which shall be the basis of the conduct of periodic training.
2. During the conduct of *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan*, topics on sustainable fishery management introduced by USAID program to stop illegal fishing must be discussed such as; a) Ecosystems Improved for Sustainable Fisheries (ECOFISH 2012-2017), a program which assist the Government of the Philippines, local governments, the private sector and stakeholders to strengthen fisheries governance, management and enforcement; b) National Stock Assessment Program (2015) which provide technical assistance to improve and standardize the program training curriculum, train new Philippine Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources field personnel on data collection in more than 250 sites and enhance the Bureau’s competencies to analyze

the exploitation statuses of economically important fisheries; c) National Oceanic Atmospheric Administration (NOAA 2014-2017) Philippine Support Program, which assist the BFAR to improve its vessel monitoring system and conducts training to fishery law enforcement agencies in setting up and analyzing information on an Alert System for Boat Detection for municipal waters and seasonal closure of critical fisheries; d) Philippines Biodiversity Program, which provides technical support to the task forces and interagency law enforcement groups to improve coordination across agencies and facilitate the investigation and prosecution of environmental crimes including those related to IUU fishing and; e) Protect Wildlife (2016-2021), This new activity aims to conserve biodiversity in key protected areas in the Philippines and demonstrate the integration of conservation and development outcomes. The activity will achieve these dual objectives using a systems approach that involves capacity building and technical assistance, conservation finance and partnerships, behavior change, science and technology and environmental law enforcement; f) Rest the Bay (2014), a program which Implemented the closed season to address economic losses for fishers, raising awareness of the importance of the closed season, and ensuring enforcement.

3. The increasing value of fishery law enforcement must be stressed by the partnership, and this can be only achieved if the expected outputs are balanced by the required training that must be conducted. Formulation of Coastal Law Enforcement Training (CLET) must be done which will be the basis of the conduct of periodic training.
4. Communication is an indispensable pre-requisite. To achieve this, open communication lines must be guaranteed with all communication devices in

order as specified in the OPLAN DALOY under the Ecosystem Improved for Sustainable Fishery (ECOFISH) program of the USAID to act immediately on the reported illegal fishing activities.

5. After the conduct of training, the creation of Fishery Law Enforcement Team (FLET) composes of Maritime Police, and Bantay Dagat must be created that will serve as a quick response team on the reported illegal fishing activities in the area.
6. Basic Intelligence subjects must be included in the POI and participants from the intelligence community must be invited to attend to maintain a close intelligence network among the law enforcer and the community for the reporting system on the intrusion of fishing vessels from nearby provinces of Batangas.
7. Policy recommendation on the creation of Municipal Fishery Council in every municipality within the Balayan Bay composed of representatives from LGU, PNP Maritime Group, BFAR-FARMC, PCG and other concern stakeholders to discuss the proposal of USAID on the livelihood programs and measures to stop illegal fishing.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is a universally accepted principle in public administration that law enforcement cannot attain the level of success if the community or the general public would not cooperate and give its support. During the past twenty years, community policing has gained popularity in police agencies worldwide. Community Oriented Policing (COP) is an approach that engages the community as an equal partner with law enforcement agencies in solving local crime and disorder problems. Studies show that community policing helps establish legitimacy and trust through meeting with community stakeholders regularly to address issues or concerns. The result is an increase in public support and cooperation with the police, leading to a more effective means of combating crime.

Although addressing the problem of criminality is primarily the job of the police in the Philippines, the much-desired personnel, logistics, and training capability to cope with crime detection and prevention activities are yet to be realized. Thus, the country needs the support of the community as a partner and force multiplier of the Philippine National Police (PNP).

Relatively, a partnership is embodied in the PNP's Vision and Mission Statement. The PNP's vision states that "Imploring the Aid of the Almighty, by 2030, we shall be a highly capable, effective, and credible police service working in partnership with a responsive community towards the attainment of a safer place to live, work and do business. Meanwhile, the PNP's mission is to "Enforce the law, prevent and control crimes, maintain peace and order, ensure public safety, and internal security with the active support of the community. Therefore, the PNP needs to revitalize and institutionalize the partnership between the police and the community because it is essential in its law enforcement functions. Hence, the PNP

must interact with them, listen to their needs, and build safer communities together with them.

The enactment of the Local Government Code in 1991(RA 7160) further strengthened community involvement. RA 7160 placed the local government at the center of national development including the promotion of peace and order in the local communities. As provided for in paragraph 12-d, Section 391 of RA 7160, the barangay may provide for the organization of community brigade, barangay *tanod*, or community service units as may be necessary to assist in the peace and order effort of the local government unit.

Relatively, RA 8550 (The Philippine Fisheries Code of 1998), provides that the LGUs shall have authority over municipal waters, rules, and regulations as well as valid fisheries ordinances enacted by the municipality/city council and may seek the assistance of the Department of Agriculture (DA) through the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR) in the training of the *Bantay Dagat* Task Force in fishery law apprehension technique. After the training, the *Bantay Dagat* will be deputized by the chief local executive as fish wardens to assist the PNP in the enforcement of fishery laws within the municipal/city waters.

On the other hand, the PNP Maritime Group (PNP MG) is one of the National Support Units of the PNP tasked to perform police functions within the Philippine territorial waters and rivers. It includes Maritime and Environmental Law Enforcement, Internal Security Operations, and Search, Rescue, And Retrieval Operations. In keeping with its effort to protect the country's marine resources, the Group has 17 Regional Maritime Units (RMU) nationwide conducting aggressive enforcement of Maritime and Environmental Law.

However, the PNP-MG has only about 1300 personnel deployed nationwide to

enforce fishery law within the Philippine coastal areas which are considered one of the longest in the world. Indeed, the responsibility of the Maritime Police to guard the territorial waters of the country is truly gigantic. This is the reason why the PNP-MG entered a partnership with the *Bantay Dagat* to intensify its campaign against illegal fishing to have a safe and secure maritime environment that can protect the marine habitat to yield a sustainable fish harvest.

The *Bantay Dagat* also known as the “Sea Patrol”, is a community-based volunteer organization that works with local and national government officials to protect the marine environment especially illegal fishing, and to assist in rescue operations. The community decided to take immediate action to reverse the decline of fish production. Since the government could not provide men to regularly patrol the sea, they decided to volunteer their services using their facilities such as boats, lights, and other needed equipment. The purpose was to stop destructive fishing practices and reduce pressure in coastal waters. The usual practice when violators were apprehended was to just issue a warning and subject the first-time offenders to a brief lecture on the importance of taking care of the coastal environment. To achieve a positive and measurable impact in coastal resource management, the government recognized that opportunities for partnership with the fisher folks/communities should be enhanced. Various laws and guidelines were issued which have strengthened the strategy.

The partnership of the Maritime Police with the *Bantay Dagat* allows each other to be more effective because joint efforts can draw upon unique professional skills, knowledge, training, and missions. This is under the Letter of Instruction (LOI) 30/200 (PNP Organizational Plan “*SAMBAYAN*” 2002), paragraph 2 (United Front Against Criminality), which states that “The PNP shall develop a united front

composed of the different sectors of the community, which shall serve as its force multiplier in the fight against all forms of criminalities. Considering the limited resources of the police force, especially in terms of manpower, the development of the various groups such as the *Bantay Dagat*, *Barangay Tanod*, and other sectors as partners of the PNP shall serve to boost its anti-crime campaign.”

The LOI is clear recognition that policing is not a function confined to the formal police force alone but a concerted effort of various sectors of the community whose main work is related to the maintenance of peace and order. The effects are far-reaching and the responsibility covers all the government’s solutions in the campaign for public involvement was further emphasized by the issuance of LOI 22/69 “*BAYANIHAN*” (Barangay Peacekeeping Operations) dated May 4, 2009, that set the guidelines in the establishment of an effective community geared towards the attainment of peace and order.

Moreover, the same order emphasized community partnership via the empowerment of people and the establishment of a lasting relationship, based on mutual respect trust, and confidence between the PNP and the community. It can be gleaned from the discussions on the community policing concept that crime prevention and proactive problem-solving are areas of special concern. And there is an important underlying situation that needs to be addressed in the partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* – the internal and external problems they encounter in their campaign against illegal fishing.

One of the major limitations of professional policing and its crime control policies is the failure of both the police and the community to elicit the full cooperation and participation of each other in the enforcement of the law. The same dilemma faced both the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat*, in terms of enforcement

of fishery law/ordinance; suppression/control of illegal fishing activities; and information gathering and dissemination.

With the above premises and consideration in the account, the Researcher seeks to study the partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat*, in their campaign against illegal fishing and the problems confronting their partnership, particularly. Is the partnership a working concept that will create a strategy to solve the problem of illegal fishing activities at Balayan Bay? And will the partnership draw greater cooperation from the community that will pave the way for the attainment of a safe and secured maritime environment and protection of marine habitat that will yield a sustainable fish harvest?

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

An effective community policing strategy will reduce neighborhood crime, eliminate citizens' fear of crime, and enhance the quality of life in the community. In this regard, an important goal of community policing is to provide quality service to the neighborhood. Therefore, an early measure of the effectiveness of the police-community partnership will evolve in the following areas such as enhanced law enforcement, prevention of crime, and timely information dissemination.

This chapter highlights the literature and studies related to the research work on the police-community partnership as well as the international and local problems involving illegal fishing. The literature and studies are presented from the general to the specific topics, considering the variables of the study.

Foreign Literature

In the past, the community's involvement effort has been limited. Many policing agencies realized that community members can be valuable sources of support and information. Citizens can provide the police with insight into the specific crime problems occurring within their neighborhoods and can aid officers in their investigation. The collaboration is beneficial to both the police and the community.

There are varieties of motives for forming a partnership. There are important reasons for law enforcement agencies to form alliances with community organizations such as to reduce crime and improve the quality of life for members of the community. For example, Community Oriented Policing (COP) is being practiced in many jurisdictions. In COP partnerships, citizens are "co-producers of public safety" and these collaborations are designed to develop the community as a partner

against criminal activity (Morabito, 2010).

Some community policing practices partner with specific groups of people within the community. In New Britain, and Connecticut, for example, law enforcement meets with business owners and other community representatives regularly as part of the “Weed and Seed “program. The program was created to help identify, arrest, and prosecute violent offenders in targeted areas and enhance the quality of police-citizen interactions (Costanza et al, 2010).

In Skogan et al. (2002), there are many types of police-community partnerships and individuals involved in these partnerships and the reasons for the affiliation are diverse. The one common theme is they all strive to build better community relationships and improve the quality of life for the members of the community.

During the past decade, there have been significant advances in joint data-sharing and problem-solving initiatives. Regional data sharing and problem-solving refer to the idea that crime-related problems can be solved more effectively when police departments collect data and share their findings with other local police agencies. The use of a geographic information system allows law enforcement agencies to collect data on crimes and to collaborate more easily and effectively with other agencies (Boba et al, 2009).

In Wilson (2009), this also makes crime analysis more accurate and is currently in use to assist in disseminating information to other law enforcement agencies, residents, and potential residents.

Due to the rapid population growth of certain minority groups, criminal justice agencies must learn ways to overcome perceptions of corruption and distrust, and the solution is to find ways to connect with members of the communities (Skogan et

al, 2002).

As a result, many communities have implemented partnerships between minority residents and law enforcers to strengthen minority confidence in the police and increase their willingness to participate in crime activities (Wehrman & DeAngelis, 2011).

In Chicago, the police have allied with members of the Latino community. The affiliation educates citizens about the law to help them avoid involvement in criminal activity (Skogan et al, 2002).

In Wehrman and DeAngelis (2011), these types of alliances connect minority communities with law enforcement and create a beneficial relationship between officers and citizens. There are many goals associated with community-based policing programs. All community policing programs, however, strive to establish and maintain a successful working relationship between law enforcement agencies and the public with the intent to reduce crime.

In Gilbert and Settles (2007), “neighborhood-restorative community justice should be indigenous to the neighborhood served. Such program is not imposed from the outside; they emerge from discussions about neighborhood problems and how best to respond to these problems by residents of the neighborhood.”

The amount of information exchanged between police agencies and citizens is important to the success of any community policing program and the public’s willingness to cooperate is evident by the number of information citizens are giving police officers regarding crimes occurring within their neighborhood (Wells et al, 2006).

Wehrman & De Angelis (2011), suggest that the underlying goals of police-community partnership should seek out ways for police departments to build a

stronger relationship with their communities. This can be done by gaining residents' confidence in the police, which will in turn create more willingness to work with the police in anti-crime initiatives. Some of the anti-crime initiatives include foot, bike, and Segway patrol. These initiatives take officers out from inside their vehicles, which many have historically been seen as a barrier between the community and law enforcement, and place them in a position for more personal contact with citizens.

The goals of Community Oriented Policing, itself an alternative to traditional law enforcement approaches, have shown the importance of increasing interactions with the community (Hickman & Reaves, 2001), which modernizes how the police operate.

To build a relationship, police can also offer opportunities to expose criminal justice students to COP practices, participate in activities that encourage trust between the police and residents, and police providing a clear message that their neighborhood does not accept violence as the norm (Mazerolle et al, 2010).

A partnership is formed based on geographic location to facilitate COP. Some police agencies give patrol officers permanent assignments to specific geographic areas so that they can involve in community organizations, establish ongoing communications with other agencies, and orchestrate opportunities for police-community interactions (Chappel, 2009).

COP is developed through organizational change within law enforcement to allow community participation. To this end, technology and community resources are being used to facilitate this integration and adapt to the differing needs of each community (Morabito, 2010).

The effective use of government resources in problem-solving is an indication that community policing is working. Some police agencies are developing websites

to create a stronger bond between the police and the community. The benefits of using websites are an increased perception of openness and accessibility to police departments, increased community trust, and the increased ability to inform the public about crime. Increased level of community participation in crime reduction and prevention efforts is another indication of program success. Community members will not be suspicious and they become more willing to work with the police in a variety of ways like involving themselves in neighborhood watch groups. They might be also comfortable providing information on criminal activity in the area. Calls to report a crime may increase considerably during the early phases of community policing implementation (Rosenbaum & Schuck, 2011).

Law enforcement agencies must also have enough personnel to assign patrol officers to small geographic areas to facilitate opportunities for interactions with residents. They should also educate patrol officers and administrators about how to implement community policing practices, offer problem-solving training, provide incentives to compliant officers, and be willing to restructure their management to promote the philosophies of community policing (Chappel, 2008).

Technology also plays an important role in community partnerships. Community crime mapping helps agencies identify and analyze problems that can lead to long-term solutions (Hickman & Reaves, 2005).

Regional data-sharing partnerships tend to work better when there is a common goal in sharing data such as solving a specific, local crime problem. To be effective, technology such as GIS mapping systems needs to be used by all of the contributing agencies. It is helpful to craft a written agreement between law enforcement and public agencies involved in data-sharing partnerships to combat confidentiality issues and establish problem-solving intentions. Because regional

data sharing across jurisdictions can be met with obstacles, it is often more productive to concentrate only on partnerships within one jurisdiction to solve local problems (Boba et al, 2009).

According to Rosenbaum & Shuck, (2011), modern computer technology has also been shown to be a best practice/community partnership. Computer databases have enabled agencies to share vital information, receive, feedback, and further interact with the community. It was found that 77.1 percent of agencies using websites allowed citizens to contact the police, and 39.6 percent allowed direct email access to police officers. If a law enforcement agency can provide a website for community members to access, then these agencies appear accessible to the public; strengthening police legitimacy and trust.

The success of a positive police/community partnership, as with most community-oriented initiatives, hinges on the involvement of each stakeholder. This includes, but is not limited to, businesses, schools, churches, city agencies, and individual community members. Research also suggests an important step when forming a community-based partnership is to consider cultural influences within the community. Official statistics demonstrate minorities and members of disadvantaged classes are overrepresented in arrest conviction, and incarceration statistics. This can lead those belonging to ethnic minority groups to believe issues such as crime and prevention strategies need to be addressed by disadvantaged communities and police instead of the community. Skogan et al. (2005), also suggests police agencies consider the ethnic make-up communications when attempting to implement police-community strategies. They further advice marketing of a police agency's community programs to be conducted in various languages and through various media, such as newspapers, radio, television, and the internet.

Foreign Studies

In the study entitled “Re-Visiting Concept and Theories of Community Policing “conducted by Universiti Putra Malaysia,” the author mentioned that concept of community policing is slowly but gradually assuming a multidimensional as well as a multifaceted idea, especially in practice. Yet, the philosophy remains singular all through the mid-'70s when the drive began to trickle down. Ever since, multitudes of literature have filed up to define, explain and theorize community policing. However, since the advent of community policing, there is no universally accepted definition. (Yero et al, 2012).

Meanwhile, law enforcement has been quietly revolutionized assuming a great source of debate as to the exact nature and scope it possesses (James, 2002). However, there is a consensus among the academia, police institutions, and governments as to the viability of moving towards community-oriented policing to reduce fear and overall attainment of quality of life, or a safe city in other instances.

Human societies are so much distinct and unique from each other. Therefore, to assume that there can be a distinct method of application of the community policing model is generalist, considering that every society revolves around certain tendencies that shape and determine the navigation routes or rather “endogenous and exogenous factors shaping its existence (Oliver, 2000).

The concept of community policing has been defined by many scholars and practitioners in various ways. These definitions have assumed categorical styles to avoid the risk of generalization. According to the Office of Community-Oriented Policing (2007), crime and social disorder is the focus of community policing. This is achieved through service delivery which includes aspects of regular law enforcement, prevention, problem-solving, as well as community engagement and

partnership. The community policing model tries to strike a balance between reactive responses with proactive problem solving specifically on the causes of crime and disorder, community policing is essentially about the partnership between the police and the citizens.

In application, visibility, and acting become the operational role of the police who try to ensure that disorder and crime are managed properly. On the part of the community information, support and feedback are required and police should respond to all concerns (Manning, 2003). At every attempt to define community policing therefore one will be inclined to know from which angle the concept is being approached, this can offer a credible insight as to what represents the viewpoint of the author. Nevertheless, having a single definition of community policing remains a fleeting illusion.

Tilley (2008) in his contribution to community policing observed that the importance of policing has to do with the people and the community rather than policing the community, it aspires to improve the quality of life, aiming to solve community problems. Beyond this, it has proven difficult to pin down what specifically is involved in implementing community policing. On this point, there exists broad agreement among scholars and many police officers.

Skolnick & Bayley (1998) concluded that viewing community policing standards around the world will identify that commonality can be an approach to community policing. These common attributes are: (a) a growing shift to "community-based crime prevention" all over the world using citizen education, neighborhood watch, and similar techniques, as opposed to relying on police patrol to prevent crime. (b) a change in direction from an emergency response (chasing calls) to proactive such as foot patrol, (c) increased accountability in the police towards the

citizen and community at large.

Partnership Theory of crime prevention emphasized that the criminal justice system cannot, by itself, solve the complex problem of crime and disorder in our society. Those resources from outside the system are desperately needed, as well as new ways of thinking about diverse problems from the inside. To achieve this, the theory advocates for the creation of a “partnership” -a group of organizations that can bring distinctive but complimentary skills and resources to the table and can produce coordinated and targeted responses to public safety (Rosenbaum, 2003).

Rosenbaum (2003) further stated “First, by “putting heads together”, a partnership may result in new, innovative approaches that would have been conceived without the “collision” and synthesis of diverse perspectives. Second, the application of resources from multiple agencies may increase the quantity of the intervention. And third, the partnership may lead to the coordinated application of resources in a manner that enhances the nature of the quality of the interventions and their effects. The presence of such synergy would serve to demonstrate that the “whole is greater than the sum of the parts.”

Hills (2011) identified another source of challenge to community policing which is “policing a plural society where inter-communal conflict, as well as inter-religious conflict, flourish”. In a situation where crime and criminality are rampant and the community that is supposed to collaborate to tackle security challenges in collaboration with the police is a party to the crime then community-oriented policing is out of the question. If the police officers are also influenced by their values and it affects their decision, then there cannot be community policing. In essence therefore community policing must be capable of moving towards the most difficult of security challenges facing human society while tackling the minor criminal elements that

could lead to crime.

It is quite evident that the prospects are good because the philosophy of community policing is being advanced as the new policing system for the twenty-first century. Certain factors will have a greater influence on the future development of community policing initiatives. The first point raised has to do with the acknowledged growing influence by people of the insecurity around them, especially about terrorism. New strategies are being adapted by community members on how to secure their neighborhood to have peace of mind and good life Palmiotto (2011).

Palmiotto also observed that a growing number of police officers are educated and the current present force has the highest number of educated personnel ever in history. Considering this fact, the transformation will be much easier and more sophisticated soon.

Based on the observed trend, we are likely to see the continued growth and expansion of community policing in practice all over the world. The successes recorded by the previous studies and achievements in implementation by various police organizations will be the source of motivation to join police organizations since other examples exist and can be learned from. It is likely that future efforts will be more precise, structured, and organized based on previous research results and experiences obtained. Mistakes recorded by pioneers on implementation will likely be avoided but new ones may arise due to the difference in nature and challenges of human societies.

Ogadimma et al (2013), stated in their study entitled "Challenge Faced by Community-Oriented Policing Training In Nigeria," community policing, just as the name implies, is a unique partnership with the public and police in crime prevention and control within the community. It is a modern policing strategy that allows the

police to proactively act beyond mere fighting and to partner with community members in setting the security priorities in society and fashioning ways of resolving identified problems in the community. This synergy between the police and the public is anchored on mutual trust and respect between both parties and could be enhanced through community policing training.

According to Arase and Iwuofor (2007), community policing has come to remodel, train, and place strategies, so that the best wields the baton, as well as elicit public cooperation and partnership in policing Nigeria. Community policing training prepares the police mentally, and physically to meet up with many demands of their job (Andrews, 2009). This partnership according to Jerome and David (1998) will make both the police and the people “co-producers of safety” in the community.

The Nigeria Police has a mission statement that aims to create a safer and more secured environment conducive to meaningful socio-economic development through community policing and crime prevention (Arase & Iwuofor, 2007). The major challenge now is how to empower the police with the needed skills through community policing training to achieve these noble goals in Nigeria.

The emergence of democracy in Nigeria has placed additional demands and challenges on both police training and operational strategies. People are now expecting the police to observe human rights and rule of law while carrying out their operations in society. Also, the global shift from the traditional approach in policing to a more humane, problem-solving, and community-participatory policing style has necessitated a commensurate change in the training of police officers in society. The reason for the emergence of community-oriented policing in Nigeria is because oftentimes citizens watch crime take place in their community without reporting because they do not want to “get involved” or they do not trust the police (Palmiotto et

al., 2000).

According to Kelling, (2008), “in this era when people from all walks of life feel angry and alienated from the government and its representatives, moving closer to the people by community-oriented policing is the present mandate to build trust with the consumers of their service.” If the police realize that they exist for the people and without working with people they cannot prevent crime, then the people should form the fulcrum or their services and activities within the community. Community policing invites citizens to collaborate with the people to establish a community-specific crime-fighting agenda. This policy also utilizes problem-solving techniques, encouraging police to seek creative, pro-active solutions to solve the community. The overarching goal of community-oriented policing should be for the police to become partners with the community and empower them so that they can make their neighborhoods safer. The main goal of community policing is to improve the crime control capacities of the police by creating an effective working relationship between the community and the police (Trojanowics & Moore, 2008).

Local Literature

In the Manual of Barangay Peacekeeping Operation and Barangay Peacekeeping Action Team (2009), Police Director General Jesus Versosa, former Chief mentioned “The involvement, support, and partnership of government institutions, agencies, and the community and citizens are necessary to attain peace, security, and safety. Thus, we must all be collectively firm in assisting preference, applying solutions, and laying down the framework for attaining peace and stability as the precursor to progress and development.” In the past, various anti-criminality strategies and concepts were adapted by the PNP in its effort to curb criminality and

maintain peace and order. However, most of the concepts were found to be unsustainable as those were revised versions of crime prevention from other countries and were not suitable to the existing situation in the Philippines.

The strength of the governance of the country lies in the basic political unit called the barangay. In Community Oriented Policing Systems (COPS), the barangay is the heart of the policing system. The precincts are located within the community wherein the policeman and the people are considered partners in promoting peace and order. In Japan, this concept is called Koban, while in Singapore it is the Neighborhood Watch Program (Versosa, 2009).

History shows that the Philippines have its way of community policing. While we adopted in the past various community policing, nevertheless, we have to resort to our homegrown policing system anchored on the community partnership called 'Bayanihan' It answers the need for the whole neighborhood to get involved in policing and law enforcement. The community relies upon the police to 'save and protect" and the police, in return, rely upon community support and cooperation to be effective (Versosa, 2009).

In the Philippine Constitution, the Declaration of Principles and State Policies states that the prime duty of the state is to serve and protect the people. The Government may call upon the people to defend the state and all the citizens may be required under conditions provided by law, to render personal, military, or civil service. The PNP recognizes the role of Barangay Tanod, Bantay Bayan, CVOs, Barangay Auxiliaries, NGOs, and people's organizations as a force multiplier, in the fight against criminality, insurgency, and terrorism. These organizations are also valuable partners of the government in community development.

In the PNP Maritime Group setting, the *Bantay Dagat* is an indispensable

partner in community policing within the coastal areas of the country. The *Bantay Dagat* is considered one of its kind in the world because no other archipelagic state like the Philippines has established a partnership with the community in terms of fishery law enforcement. *Bantay Dagat* is the term coined to describe the practice of sea patrol by volunteers. The strategy originated in Cebu in the 1970s and was conceptualized when illegal fishing and over-exploitation of marine resources were so rampant in the area causing an alarming decrease in the community's fish catch. The threat was that if fish catch continued to decrease, meeting the fish requirement of the community would even be more difficult.

In the Philippine Fisheries Code of 1998 (Republic Act 8550), as amended by RA 10654, it is stipulated in its provision that members of fisher folks associations may be designated by the Department of Agriculture as fish wardens in the enforcement of fishery laws, rules, and regulations, provided they have undergone training on law enforcement.

The above law also mandates various government agencies, such as the Department of Environment and Natural Resources, Department of Agriculture, Department of Interior and Local Government, Philippine Coast Guard, etc., and other agencies concerned with the management, protection, conservation, and development of fisheries and aquatic resources to provide continuous technical assistance to the Fisheries and Aquatic Resources Management Council (FARMC). The assistance includes organizational strengthening, law enforcement, legal and human right assistance, fisherfolk settlement, and training, among others. BFAR monitors the assistance extended to the Council at all levels.

The government also created a West Philippine Sea Anti-Illegal Fishing Task Force mainly to address such activities off Zambales following complaints by local

fishers. Agriculture Secretary Emmanuel F. Piñol had instructed Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR) national director Eduardo Gongona to head the task force. Gongona, for his part, said the BFAR would use its resources to ensure the enforcement of Philippine fishing laws. The fisherfolk informed them about the illegal and unsustainable fishing practices, which continue to hound the municipal fisherfolk among these are blast fishing and entry of suspected foreign poachers. Piñol promised to provide lawyers to aid in the prosecution of violators (Domingo, 2017).

The Philippine government said it will launch a clampdown on illegal fishing in a campaign that is as severe as President Rodrigo Duterte's war on drugs and criminality and administrative charges will be slapped against local officials who failed to stop illegal fishing in their area. He said during the last cabinet meeting, Duterte had called on mayors and barangay (district) towns and villages where illegal fishing was prevalent to be identified and gave them six months to comply. (Yan, 2017).

Comparing the approach to that used in the ongoing war on drugs shows how seriously the government is taking the issue of illegal fishing. Since Duterte entered office in June, more than 6,000 people have been killed in his war on drugs, almost half of which died at the hands of police while the others were murdered by vigilante groups. Threats were also extended to corrupt officials who he claimed would suffer the same fate as drug suspects and hardened criminals. Along with the threat of punishment for failing to curb illegal fishing, success will be rewarded with the government planning to present the "most outstanding coastal community" with a presidential award. The winning community will be selected based on several criteria, including the total eradication of illegal fishing, sustainable fishing seasons, and declaring marine sanctuaries, and coastal waters clear of garbage, among

others (Calvan, 2017).

Three years after the amendments of the Fisheries Code, data from the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR) showed an increasing number of reported violations from 254 in 2016 to 894 in 2017. This indicates that the law has not deterred illegal fishing in the country. Foremost of these is the encroachment of commercial fishing vessels, the use of Danish seines and Modified Danish Seines or *hulbot-hulbot*, plus dynamite and cyanide fishing within 15 km of municipal waters. Illegal commercial and destructive fishing drastically destroys the productivity of our oceans – causing the country to lose about PHP44 Billion in fishing revenues yearly, apart from heavily impacting the livelihoods of our artisanal fisherfolk. A call for the government and all stakeholders to remain steadfast in stopping illegal fishing and for BFAR to suspend or revoke licenses of fisheries law violators was urged (Calvan, 2017).

Based on a 2017 Social Weather Station study that was commissioned by Oceana, around 43% of Filipinos believe that illegal fishing is a serious problem. Most of them believe that proper fisheries management and strict enforcement of fishery laws can address illegal fishing.

U.S. Embassy in the Philippines' United States Agency for International Development (USAID), the Southeast Asia Fisheries Development Center (SEAFDEC), and the government of the Philippines, through its Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR), launched a partnership in support of The Oceans and Fisheries Partnership (USAID Oceans). The program will enhance the sustainability of Asia-Pacific fisheries, protect the region's rich marine biodiversity, and mitigate the serious impacts that result from illegal and unregulated fishing. USAID Oceans works with the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) and

Coral Triangle member countries to enhance catch documentation and traceability, fisheries management, and human welfare. As hundreds from the fisheries sector gather at the 18th Annual Tuna Congress in General Santos City, USAID Oceans and BFAR announced the partnership and the launch of a learning site in the area, which will serve as a model for regional learning and expansion (Domingo, 2017).

More than 50 million Filipinos are dependent on fish as a source of food, while the fisheries sector employs nearly three million people – of which 70 are municipal fisherfolks, according to non-government Oceana (FAO, 2016). But alarming figures released by the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resource showed that 10 out of 13 major fishing grounds surveyed in the country are already over fished. The government's effort to charge local officials who failed to perform their duties is laudable because irresponsible fishing has reduced many wild fish populations to historically low levels right at the moment when the world needs its oceans more than ever (Oceana, 2016).

Illegal and unreported fishing has serious impacts. In the Philippines alone, over 450 tons of fish are caught using illegal practices each year, resulting in annual economic losses of up to \$620 million according to Alfred Nakatsuma, Director of the Regional Environment Office at the USAID Regional Development Mission for Asia. The effects are felt across the Asia-Pacific region, with decreasing fish stocks that threaten global food stocks and livelihoods, as well as human welfare abuses that marginalize millions and claim lives. There is a global movement occurring to improve the ocean's health, enhance the sustainability of fisheries, and increase accountability throughout the seafood supply chain, and there is a commitment to deepen the engagement through partnership for the long-term well-being of the oceans (USAID Oceans, 2015).

The journal *Science* published a four-year study in November 2006, which predicted that, at prevailing trends, the world would run out of wild-caught seafood in 2048. The scientists stated that the decline was a result of overfishing, pollution, and other environmental factors that were reducing the population of fisheries at the same time as their ecosystems were being annihilated. Yet again the analysis has met criticism as being fundamentally flawed, and many fishery management officials, industry representatives, and scientists challenge the findings, although the debate continues. Many countries, such as Tonga, the United States, Australia, and Bahamas, and international management bodies have taken steps to appropriately manage marine resources (Journal Science, 2006).

The Philippine government launched a clampdown on illegal fishing in a campaign that is as severe as President Rodrigo Duterte's war on drugs and criminality. Administrative charges will be slapped against local officials who failed to stop illegal fishing in their area. Duterte had called on mayors and barangay (district) towns and villages where illegal fishing was prevalent to prevent these acts and gave them six months to comply (Domingo, 2017).

The government must step up with its enforcement efforts against illegal, unreported, and unregulated fishing (IUUF) if it hopes to meet the fisheries output target for the year, an advocate for ethical fishing practices said. According to Dennis F. Galvan, Network Representative of *Pangingsda Natin Gawing Tama* (PANAGAT), Illegal fishing alone in the municipal fisheries sector, we are losing around 257,000 to 402,000 metric tons (MT) of fish a year, which amounts to P24 to P37.8 billion.

Oceana Vice-President Gloria E. Ramos said that Illegal fishing has remained a problem even if there is a law. The intrusion of commercial fishers in municipal waters caused this problem of overfishing and fish stocks are continuously decreasing at an alarming rate. This has caused unjust suffering to poor artisanal fisherfolk so the government has to live up to its mandate to protect the coastal communities' livelihood and the food security of the Filipino people (Jocson LMCJ, (2022), Illegal fishing crackdown is seen as a key to meeting output goals.

Illegal fishing appeared to spike during the Philippines' lockdown period as commercial fishers took advantage of reduced patrols to ply coastal waters that they're prohibited from fishing in, satellite tracking data indicate. The months of March to May are prime fishing seasons in the Philippines, ahead of the start of the monsoon in July, when sailing conditions become difficult. This fishing period coincided with the lockdown imposed by the government in response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

But that didn't stop illegal fishing, according to aggregated data from Karagatan Patrol, an online reporting platform that's a collaboration between the nonprofit group Oceana Philippines and the country's League of Municipalities to counter illegal fishing. Karagatan Patrol tracks ships through VIIRS (visible infrared imaging radiometer suite), a satellite-based tool that detects the high-radiance lure lights used by commercial fishing vessels. Oceana attributed the increase in apparent illegal fishing during the lockdown period to the fact that "some enforcement agencies were diverted to other COVID-19-related tasks. As a result, illegal fishers took advantage of the lack of monitoring, she said. But some municipalities in the Philippines joined forces to "enhance enforcement of fisheries and environmental laws in their municipal waters" (Mongabay, 2020).

The *Bantay Dagat* organization currently has a total of 433 volunteer members from 15 coastal local government units in Batangas province who cooperate in patrolling and monitoring the beaches and oceans against illegal activities. This was reported by the Provincial Government Environment and Natural Resources Office (PGENRO), saying the Bantay Dagat volunteers wholeheartedly and courageously serve to protect the marine protected areas and the entire municipal waters against destructive activities, despite the dangers and possible threats to their lives (Magsombol, 2021).

Other programs being implemented by other government agencies and non-government organizations to stop illegal fishing are also being undertaken to support the PNP Maritime Group. The Ecosystems Improved for Sustainable Fisheries (ECOFISH 2012-2017) under the USAID assisted the Government of the Philippines, local governments, the private sector and stakeholders to strengthen fisheries governance, management and enforcement. In partnership with the Philippine Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources, USAID supported enabling policies and provided tools to address IUU fishing. The Ecosystems Improved for Sustainable Fisheries project assisted with multi-stakeholder consultations in preparation for the implementation of the rules and regulations in RA 10654, which was approved in September 2015.

With USAID's support, the Philippine Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources provided training to fisheries officers to detect, analyze and document fish caught illegally with explosives. The Bureau also published the first Fish Examiners' Training Manual in June 2016. USAID partnered with the Philippine Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources to support registration and licensing schemes in the municipal fisheries sector as a key deterrent to IUU fishing. With

USAID support, the first nationwide municipal fisheries registration program was established in 2013 to determine allocation priorities, limiting entry into municipal water and monitoring fishing activities. More than 1.5 million of the estimated 1.7 million municipal fishers have registered in the program to date. In addition, a registration of municipal fishing vessels and gear programs was launched in 2015. USAID provides ongoing technical assistance to enhance the efficiency of the bureau's online registration system and to enact enabling legislation on registration for at least 60 municipal governments across the country.

In partnership with the Philippine Department of Science and Technology and Microsoft, USAID supported the pilot of television white space for municipal fisherfolk registration in Bohol province. Television white space repurposes unused broadcast frequencies to provide high speed wireless Internet access at a low cost and with minimal infrastructure requirements, making it a promising solution in developing countries. With successful implementation, over 16,000 fisherfolk have been registered in the pilot — nearly a quarter through television white space. Government agencies are using this registration data to design and deploy better fisheries management interventions to address overfishing, monitor illegal fishing and provide alternative livelihoods. Following the success of the television white space pilot, the Government of Philippines has taken the leadership role in replicating the technology in other locations to support the goal of providing wireless Internet access to 99 percent of the population.

USAID also supports the Philippine National Police Maritime Group in implementing an anonymous hotline that allows local communities to report illegal fishing. The hotline, 700DALOY, crowdsources illegal fishing detection, helping local government and maritime police better coordinate enforcement. In a six-month pilot

in Tawi Tawi, the hotline received more than 3,000 reports, leading to 25 arrests and the recovery of fish worth more than \$1 million. The United Nations Environmental Program awarded the Philippine National Police Maritime Group with the first Asia Environmental Enforcement Award for its achievements. USAID also provided support to the maritime police to scale up 700DALOY to include seven more marine key biodiversity areas. In September 2016, the group launched the 700DALOY information management system to improve the collection, retrieval and analysis of maritime law violations.

The National Stock Assessment Program is a key government program to monitor Philippine fisheries. USAID provided technical assistance to improve and standardize the program training curriculum, train new Philippine Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources field personnel on data collection in more than 250 sites and enhance the Bureau's competencies to analyze the exploitation statuses of economically important fisheries. With USAID assistance, the government published a State of the Marine Resources Report in June 2016; the report helps improve the fisheries regulation, including actions to address IUU fishing.

In partnership with USAID, NOAA works with the US National Oceanic Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) to provide support for government-to-government scientific and technical exchange, capacity building, technical assistance, and peer-to-peer exchanges to address IUU fishing including improved implementation of fisheries management plans and enhanced competencies in implementing marine park protection measures. With NOAA's assistance, the Government of Philippines will improve the use of fisheries management data and analysis and increase coordination among the government agencies involved in regulating fisheries and marine resources.

NOAA is assisting Philippine Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources to improve its vessel monitoring system. With USAID support, NOAA is training the Bureau and other enforcement agencies in setting up and analyzing information on an Alert System for Boat Detection for municipal waters and seasonal closure of critical fisheries.

In partnership with the U.S. Department of the Interior's International Technical Assistance Program, USAID support the Philippine Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resource's 700 new fisheries law enforcement officers in enhancing their competencies on addressing IUU fishing. The new enforcers will be trained using the Fishery Law Enforcement Training module, incorporating the Fishery Law Enforcement Manual of Operations developed with assistance from the program. Continuing assistance will also be provided to the Bureau's Fisheries Law Enforcement Management Information System, a system for tracking and managing maritime violations. The Bureau designed and developed the System with technical assistance from the program and the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service's Law Enforcement Management Information System developers.

The U.S. Department of the Interior's International Technical Assistance Program provides technical support to the task forces and interagency law enforcement groups to improve coordination across agencies and facilitate the investigation and prosecution of environmental crimes including those related to IUU fishing.

This new activity aims to conserve biodiversity in key protected areas in the Philippines and demonstrate the integration of conservation and development outcomes. The activity will achieve these dual objectives using a systems approach that involves capacity building and technical assistance, conservation finance and

partnerships, behavior change, science and technology and environmental law enforcement.

The activity will address issues in illegal wildlife trade, illegal logging, and illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing—all serious environmental crimes in the biodiversity hotspot. The activity represents USAID's support to U.S. Executive Order 13648—Combating Wildlife Trafficking and the U.S. Presidential Memorandum on the Comprehensive Framework to Combat Illegal, Unreported, and Unregulated Fishing and Seafood Fraud as well as to Philippine programs on the same (UASID, 2020).

With the theme "*Programang Pagpapautang tungo sa Progresibong Pangkabuhayan sa Pangisdaan,*" the forum aims to help fisherfolk, fisheries cooperatives, associations, and organizations, as well as Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) and other fisheries stakeholders in venturing into profitable, emerging and sustainable fishery-based endeavors through credit financing- Sammy Malvas, Regional Director BFAR IV-A.

Effective law enforcement in Tañon Strait to address illegal commercial fishing in municipal waters is proof that through political will, inter-agency cooperation, and collaboration with stakeholders, deterring and stopping illegal commercial fishing bring benefits to artisanal fishers and our marine ecosystems.

Oceana launched its nationwide campaign to stop commercial fishing in municipal waters through the establishment of an online platform, Karagatan Patrol, in partnership with the League of Municipalities of the Philippines. Karagatan Patrol reports illegal fishing in municipal waters and shares information with members of the local government, security and enforcement agencies, fisherfolk, industry players, and media.

Commercial fishing boat detection maps are shared with subscribers to show possible intrusions of commercial fishing vessels in municipal waters. These maps are based on the Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) data and enhanced by Oceana by overlaying municipal water boundaries based on the archipelagic principle, protected areas, fisheries management areas, and exclusive economic zone or EEZ.

The enforcer-members of Karagatan Patrol use these maps to plan enforcement activities that led to successful arrests. The members use the platform to share enforcement activities, report ongoing illegal fishing, and incidences of illegal fishing methods such as bottom trawling and dynamite fishing. Karagatan Patrol has also gained recognition as a game changer in reporting illegal fishing methods in the Philippine media that used the platform as source of information for their coverage of these illegal activities including poaching by foreign fishing vessels in Philippine waters.

Strong enforcement action against illegal commercial fishing in municipal waters is necessary especially that both commercial and municipal fisheries production have declined in the past 10 years. Appropriate use of technology such as vessel monitoring measures, effective enforcement, and requiring compliance by national and local authorities and commercial fishing operators are needed to ensure the sustainable management of fisheries resources in the Philippines.

A momentous victory for our oceans, the Department of Agriculture finally issued the rules on vessel monitoring measures for all commercial fishing vessels on October 12, 2020. Oceana and its partners continuously urged the agencies of the implementation of the vessel monitoring measures requirement to cover all commercial fishing vessels in the Philippines as mandated by the amended Fisheries

Code of the Philippines (Republic Act 10654). Once fully operationalized, the identity and activities of fishing vessels can be monitored electronically, this will deter irresponsible behavior and may result in significant impact on the current enforcement capabilities of national government agencies and local government units (Oceana, 2022).

In 2014, the decline in catch had become so pervasive in Balayan Bay that several commercial fishers were willing to temporarily stop fishing to allow the fish populations to regenerate. The local government units welcomed the idea, but they did not know how to develop the process and enforce a closed fishing area at a specific time of the year, for a specific length of time, while also providing for people who would lose their livelihoods as a result. ECOFISH therefore initiated a study to inform the decision on a closed season and simultaneously developed a program to build provincial government capacity to collect and analyze data on fish catch, fishing effort, and spawning period of abundant and commonly caught fish species. Using participatory methodologies, the study provided practical knowledge and clear scientific information for stakeholders to develop different scenarios for the closed season.

ECOFISH engaged stakeholders in the decision to “rest the bay” by establishing a technical working group led by the provincial government. The working group included representatives from the local governments, national government agencies, commercial fishing industry groups, and small-scale fishing associations. The provincial government then led consensus-building discussions among fishers, fishing industry players, and policy-makers to identify options that would achieve ecological goals and minimize potential economic impacts of a seasonal closure on the poor and resource-dependent small-scale fishers. The group met every two to

three months for nearly a year and then weekly right before and during the closure period. Stakeholders agreed a seasonal closure could provide overfished species the time needed to reproduce and also ensure their resilience to climate variability and other disturbances.

Implementing the closed season required addressing economic losses for fishers, raising awareness of the importance of the closed season, and ensuring enforcement. During the closure, the affected fishers worked on coastal cleanup projects in exchange for a wage that was comparable to their lost fishing income. ECOFISH developed and implemented a communications plan on the closure. The municipalities issued local ordinances and launched public information campaigns to inform fishers about both the closed season and cash-for-work program. During the closure's first year, the technical working group reported that the general public had increased awareness of the need to conserve the species protected through the closure. Finally, ECOFISH built the capacity of local government units to apply an ecosystem approach to fisheries management (EAFM). The Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources, supported by the Philippines' Coast Guard and Maritime Police, monitored the closure in coordination with the technical working group. This coordination strengthened inter-agency collaboration and increased institutional capacities for fisheries management and fishery law enforcement.

ECOFISH monitored biophysical, socioeconomic, and governance conditions at the start, middle, and end of the activity. The baseline and subsequent monitoring data served as reference points to monitor and evaluate interventions and also as inputs to planning and implementing fisheries management initiatives. ECOFISH also shared these data with stakeholders and resource users in fisheries management. To monitor biodiversity, ECOFISH collected fisheries catch data and

reef fish biomass. To measure socioeconomic changes, the team measured variables that would indicate better or new employment at the household and community levels, including household incomes, household expenditures, resource uses, environmental perceptions, and employment. Finally, ECOFISH collected data on the capacity of local governments to implement EAFM and measured improvement in law enforcement capabilities, using an EAFM governance benchmarking tool. After the first pilot closed season, ECOFISH convened the technical working group and other stakeholders to share results, which showed the closure's effectiveness in fish stock recovery (Guieb, 2020).

III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

The study will focus on the assessment of the partnership of the Maritime Police, and, *Bantay Dagat* in their campaign against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay.

The general problem of the study will focus on the assessment but will, moreover attempt to answer the following questions:

1. How do the respondents assess the partnership of the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay in terms of:
 - 1.1 Innovative Approaches and
 - 1.2 Application of Resources
 - 1.3 Coordinative Activities?

2. What are the problems encountered by the partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay in terms of:
 - 2.1 Innovative Approaches
 - 2.2 Application of Resources
 - 2.3 Coordinative Activities?

3. What measures can be proposed to address the problems encountered by the partnership of Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay relative to the afore-cited variables?

IV.OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The findings of this study present relevant data and insights on the campaign against illegal fishing by the partnership of the Maritime Police, coastal barangay officials, and *Bantay Dagat*. Specifically, the results would have significance to the following, to wit:

Local Government Unit. The findings of this study will provide the Local Government Unit with the importance of the partnership between the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* in the enforcement of fishery laws and ordinances nationwide. The result of this study will also be utilized as a basis for further improving the level of performance of the partnership through the provision of logistical and financial support as well as a guide to support the implementation of the recommended action plan.

Community. Specifically, the fisher folks and the residents of the coastal local barangays will be benefitted if the result of the partnership will improve the enforcement of fishery laws/ordinance; prevention of illegal fishing, and information sharing that will have geared towards a safe and secure maritime environment and protection of marine habitat that will yield a sustainable fish catch.

Philippine National Police. The result of the study will be useful to further strengthen the existing partnership between the Maritime Police, *Bantay Dagat*, and coastal barangay officials. It will also be a guide in improving the partnership between the police and community against illegal fishing nationwide.

Bantay Dagat. This study will give them valuable insights as to the importance of coordinative activities in terms of fishery law/ordinance enforcement, prevention of illegal fishing, and information sharing.

Future Researchers. The result of the study may provide useful data and information that could help in the conduct of their research activity on the same or related study.

V. RATIONALE

This study was conceptualized due to the importance of the partnership between the police and the community to address the problem of illegal fishing. Considering the widespread effect of illegal fishing, there is a need to involve the community in totally eradicating the problem if not then minimizing it within a manageable level.

With 7,100 islands and 18,000 kilometers of shoreline, the Philippines is a maritime nation dependent to a major extent on a healthy coastal environment. Indeed, Philippine coastal areas have served as the lifeblood of communities near and far for hundreds if not thousands of years. Unfortunately, many serious problems exist in coastal areas that are causing the natural productivity of the marine habitat to be compromised and degraded. One reason that destroyed these marine sanctuaries is illegal fishing.

The above view is under the 1987 Constitution which provides that “The State shall protect the rights of subsistence fishermen, especially the local communities, to the preferential use of communal marine and fishing resources. The Constitution also provides that the “State shall protect, develop, and conserve those resources (Section 7, Article XIII).

In view thereof, the desired partnership between the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* is an emerging concept of responsible policing that aims to curb the illegal fishing activities in Balayan Bay. This is an effective partnership because *Bantay Dagat* is a participatory approach designed for coastal law enforcement. It was founded in 1994 at the behest of then-Senator Santanina S. Rasul and they work with the DA and DILG among others.

The *Bantay Dagat* members are usually trained and deputized as fish warden that contributes to eradicating illegal fishing methods such as the use of dynamite and cyanide. While coastal barangay officials assist in raising the level of community awareness concerning environmental protection and fisheries management. As a result, it will increase the daily fish catches and greater municipal revenues from fisheries.

In line with this development, the Local Government Code of 1991 also provides the constitutional policy framework in the country that ensures local government autonomy through the decentralization of governance from national to local government. This will enable the local government units with the mandate and responsibility to develop and implement effective law enforcement programs as part of their fisheries and coastal management strategies. The important aspect of this is the enforcement of fishery regulations through effective monitoring and surveillance as well as the apprehension of violators.

Theoretical Framework

The Study draws its theoretical framework from the Partnership Theory of crime prevention by Dennis P. Rosenbaum (2003) which emphasized that the criminal justice system cannot, by itself, solve the complex problem of crime and disorder in our society. Those resources from outside the system are desperately needed, as well as new ways of thinking about diverse problems from the inside. To achieve this, the theory advocates for the creation of a “partnership” -a group of organizations that can bring distinctive but complimentary skills and resources to the table and can produce coordinated and targeted responses to public safety (Rosenbaum, 2003).

Based on Rosenbaum's Theory, a partnership is the best approach to dealing with problems of crime in the community. According to him, many people believed that community policing involving police-public partnerships in crime prevention is the best form of policing. However, anti-crime partnerships, notwithstanding their theoretical strength, face numerous problems affecting their law enforcement functions. As observed and summarized by Rosenbaum in his study, the basic problems confronting the partnership involved the enforcement of laws, crime prevention/control, and information sharing.

Rosenbaum also mentioned that the above assumptions and postulates offer some clues to formulate a conceptual framework involving mechanisms or processes by which solutions are developed. In sum, several avenues are hypothesized for the partnership to outperform single-agency approaches to crime prevention and control. First, by "putting heads together," a partnership may result in new, **innovative approaches** that would have been conceived without the "collision" and synthesis of diverse perspectives. Second, the **application of resources** from multiple agencies may increase the quantity of the intervention. And third, the partnership may lead to the **coordinated application of resources** in a manner that enhances the nature of the quality of the interventions and their effects. The presence of such synergy would serve to demonstrate that the "whole is greater than the sum of the parts" (Rosenbaum, 2003). To sum up the three observations by Rosenbaum, an effective partnership should work on law enforcement, crime prevention, and information sharing to achieve its goal.

The Partnership Theory approach is anchored in the principle that no single agency alone can succeed in reducing crime. The fact is acknowledged by security experts who argued that any comprehensive study to reduce crime must not only

include the contribution of the police and criminal justice system but also the whole range of environmental, social, economic, and educational factors which affect the likelihood of crime. To this end, many countries of the world due to ravaging security challenges and the apparent inability of the conventional police to handle the situation alone satisfactorily have encouraged the establishment of a partnership between government organizations in addressing crime. Increasingly, comparative experience has shown that this approach of incorporating a professional police service and a responsible public seems to be the most effective and fruitful way to achieve results and create a safer environment.

Conceptual Framework

Maritime Police can effectively address the problems of illegal fishing with the assistance of the community-based *Bantay Dagat*, and coastal barangay officials in terms of innovative approaches, application of resources, and coordinative activities in performing its fishery law enforcement functions. Therefore, this conceptual framework will create an environment where these institutions can work together based on the above variables to have a good relationship to attain a safe and secured maritime environment that will yield a sustainable fish harvest and will benefit the people.

The success of the partnership will depend the coordination and cooperation of both Maritime Police and Bantay Dagat through a combination of manpower resources and skills. The partnership can be vital also with the support of the government and non-government organizations. Nevertheless, no matter how noble the intention of building a partnership with the community is, there are still problems that exist that need to be addressed. These problems include law enforcement,

crime prevention and information sharing This scenario has been the product of innovation of the established partnership worldwide.

From the above studies, it appears that partnership policy has proved to be rewarding in crime prevention and control. It is observed that, with no single practical model designed to avert the aforementioned countries. Each country is tailoring the concept of partnership to suit its crime problem. This explanation shows how partnership policing should be operationalized. Success stories have shown that to create safety in all communities, local participants must adopt various partnership techniques to suit their needs. This principle of seeking local solutions to local issues is important for the development of partnerships, where there are diverse communities of people living side by side with diverse techniques for law enforcement, crime prevention, and control and information sharing.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework on the campaign strategy of the Maritime Police and Bantay Dagat against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay.

The conceptual framework is based on the systematic approach known as the input-process-output system wherein it presents the variables such as innovative approach, application of resources, and coordinative activities, the process through survey questionnaires, interviews, and documentary analysis to be undergone, and the expected output of the study. In Figure 4, the input of the study is the conduct of *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan* to inform the residents of the coastal community of the bad effects of illegal fishing: implementation of fishery law enforcement, and creation of fishery law enforcement team.

In support of the above concept, the partnership of the Maritime Police, coastal barangay officials, and *Bantay Dagat* must be developed and strengthened at the local level. Benchmarks of law enforcement must address human resource development, equipment needs, and technical expertise. The pool of Maritime Police trained in coastal law enforcement must be assigned in coastal areas while community-based *Bantay Dagat* must be trained to assist the Maritime Police in gathering intelligence, patrolling municipal waters, reporting violations, and conducting Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) on the illegal effects of fishing.

The concept of the partnership must pay attention to the inter-organizational capacity to respond with creativity in law enforcement, intensity in crime prevention, and coordination of interventions in sharing of information. The proposed conceptual framework of partnership suggests that intervention has many important characteristics that predict success such as proper fishery law enforcement, enhanced crime prevention against illegal fishing, and timely information sharing. Coalitions can reach across organizational boundaries and to reach outside the local community to leverage relevant resources considering the benefits it will reap in the

future such as sustainable fish harvest. The partnership is also hypothesized to have greater flexibility and more options for responding to local problems, including the capacity to employ additional patrol boats to complement the combined force of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat*.

VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATION

This study will focus on the partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay in the province of Batangas. The locale of the study focused on the seven (7) coastal municipalities along the Balayan bay in the province of Batangas namely; Balayan, Calatagan, Lemery, Taal, San Luis, Bauan, and Mabini. Balayan Bay is a large bay on Luzon Island in the Philippines. It is part of the Verde Island Passage and its entire shore is in the province of Batangas. The Bay is between 23 to 28 kilometers (14 to 17 mi) wide. It is separated from the South China Sea to the west by the Calatagan Peninsula, which has Cape Santiago as its southern point. The Calumpan Peninsula forms the bay's eastern side, which separates it from Batangas Bay.

The study will be limited to the partnership of the Maritime Police assigned in the province of Batangas and members of *Bantay Dagat*, in the seven coastal municipalities along Balayan Bay. It will be limited to three specific aspects namely; innovative approaches, application of resources, and coordinative activities.

The scope of reference of the study is the crime statistics of illegal fishing in Balayan Bay covering the five years from 2017-2021. The study will be conducted in the last quarter of the calendar year 2022.

The respondents of the study included the thirty-six (36) Maritime Police assigned in the province of Batangas and forty-five (45) *Bantay Dagat* members composed of seven (7) each from the coastal municipalities and fifty-nine (59) residents of coastal barangay in the seven coastal municipalities along Balayan Bay composed of ten (10) each from the seven (7) coastal municipality.

VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

The locale of the study focused on the seven (7) coastal municipalities along the Balayan bay in the province of Batangas namely; Balayan, Calatagan, Lemery, Taal, San Luis, Bauan, and Mabini. Balayan Bay is a large bay on Luzon Island in the Philippines. It is part of the Verde Island Passage and its entire shore is in the province of Batangas. The Bay is between 23 to 28 kilometers (14 to 17 mi) wide. It is separated from the South China Sea to the west by the Calatagan Peninsula, which has Cape Santiago as its southern point. The Calumpan Peninsula forms the bay's eastern side, which separates it from Batangas Bay.

Figure 2. Map of Balayan Bay showing the direction showing the intrusion of fishing vessels coming from other provinces to commit illegal fishing.

Note: Regional Maritime Police Office 4-A Accomplishment Report, 2022.

The above figures show the origin of the arrows representing fishing vessels going into Balayan Bay. This indicates that the entry point of these vessels from other provinces is between the waters of Calatagan and Mabini. The implication of this situation if not properly address will continue the entry of fishing vessel coming from nearby provinces of Batangas considering abundance of fish within the Verde Passage wherein Balayan Bay is a part. It has been observed by the fisherfolks in the area, most of incidents of reported illegal fishing were perpetrated by the intrusion of fishing vessels from another nearby province. These illegal fishers were not apprehended due to the absence of Maritime Police and Bantay Dagat in the area. Recommended solution is to established Maritime Police Station at Calatagan and Mabini to serves as police visibility in the area.

Table 1

Breakdown of the Number of Incidents of Illegal Fishing at Balayan Bay (CY 2017-2021)

Coastal Municipalities along Balayan Bay	Incidents of Illegal Fishing at Balayan Bay (CY 2017-2021)					
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	TOTAL
Mabini	0	1	3	4	3	11
Bauan	2	2	4	5	6	19
San Luis	2	3	4	6	7	22
Taal	1	3	4	5	7	20
Lemery	3	2	3	3	4	15
Calatagan	5	8	10	13	15	51
Balayan	2	3	5	5	6	21
TOTAL	15	22	33	41	48	

Note: Regional Maritime Police Office 4-A Accomplishment Report, 2022.

The above shows the breakdown of the distribution of the incidents of illegal fishing in Balayan Bay covering the 5 years from 2017-2021. The Municipality of Calaca has the highest number of recorded illegal fishing incidents which has a total

of 51 incidents compared to Mabini which recorded the lowest incident totaling 11. These incidents were reported by fisherfolks and concerned citizen in the area and mostly violators were not apprehended because of late reporting and lack or no presence of Maritime Police and Bantay Dagat due to depleted number assigned in the area.

Table 2

Status of Prosecution of Reported Illegal Fishing Activities at Balayan Bay

Coastal Municipalities	Violation/Offence Committed	Number of Prosecuted and Meted Fine	Number of Under Prosecution/ Pending Case/ Dismissed	Number of Unsolved Cases (Violators eluded arrest because of late reporting)
Mabini	- Sec. 86 Para (a) for RA 10654 (Unauthorized Fishing) - Sec. 93 RA 10654 - Sec. 95 of RA 8850 as amended by RA 10654 (Use of Active Gear) Municipal Ordinance	7	0	4
Bauan	- Sec. 86 Para (a) for RA 10654 (Unauthorized Fishing) - Sec. 93 RA 10654 - Sec. 95 of RA 8850 as amended by RA 10654 (Use of Active Gear) Municipal Ordinance	8	0	11
San Luis	- Sec. 86 Para (a) for RA 10654 (Unauthorized Fishing) - Sec. 93 RA 10654 - Sec. 95 of RA 8850 as amended by RA 10654 (Use of Active Gear) Municipal Ordinance	9	0	13
Taal	- Sec. 86 Para (a) for RA 10654 (Unauthorized Fishing) - Sec. 93 RA 10654 - Sec. 95 of RA 8850 as	7	0	13

Coastal Municipalities	Violation/Offence Committed	Number of Prosecuted and Meted Fine	Number of Under Prosecution/ Pending Case/ Dismissed	Number of Unsolved Cases (Violators eluded arrest because of late reporting)
Lemery	amended by RA 10654 (Use of Active Gear) Municipal Ordinance - Sec. 86 Para (a) for RA 10654 (Unauthorized Fishing) - Sec. 93 RA 10654 - Sec. 95 of RA 8850 as amended by RA 10654 (Use of Active Gear)	11	0	4
Calatagan	Municipal Ordinance - Sec. 86 Para (a) for RA 10654 (Unauthorized Fishing) - Sec. 93 RA 10654 - Sec. 95 of RA 8850 as amended by RA 10654 (Use of Active Gear)	16	0	35
Balayan	Municipal Ordinance - Sec. 86 Para (a) for RA 10654 (Unauthorized Fishing) - Sec. 93 RA 10654 - Sec. 95 of RA 8850 as amended by RA 10654 (Use of Active Gear)	5	0	16

Note: Regional Maritime Police Office 4-A Accomplishment Report, 2022.

Table 3**Common Profile of Illegal Fishing Violators at Balayan Bay**

Profile	Description
Nationality	All Filipino
Residence	Majority came from coastal barangays of Balayan Bay while some came from Mindoro and Quezon Province
Sex	All Male
Age	Ranges from 25- 55 years old
Marital Status	Majority are married and some are single
Educational Attainment	High school level to high school Graduate
Number of years as fisherfolk	Ranges from 5 to 20 years
Group Affiliation	No group; Unarmed; Commercial Vessel Fisherfolks
Motive in committing violations	Majority are not aware they are committing violations; Living below poverty line; To have easy and big fish catch; No stable income; No other source of livelihood
Criminal Record	Majority are first-time offenders

Note: Regional Maritime Police Office 4-A Accomplishment Report, 2022

Based on the above, all offenders are all Filipinos, males, mostly married, high school level to high school graduates, with age ranging from 25 to 55, with no group affiliation or member of syndicate or organized crime group. Most of them are not aware of the violations they committed and they commit such offence because they want to have easy and big fish catch because they have no stable income and no other source of livelihood.

Figure 3. Graphical representation of the increasing trend of illegal fishing in Balayan Bay from CY 2017-2021.

Note: Adapted from 2022 Accomplishment Report of Batangas Maritime Police Station

The above graph shows that despite the number of IUU incidents still within the manageable level, the trend is increasing within five years. The Researcher perceived that although the *Bantay Dagat* is helpful to Maritime Police in the campaign against illegal fishing, the trend of illegal fishing in Balayan Bay will decrease in number in the coming years if the problem of the partnership will be

properly addressed.

The Researcher having been in PNP Maritime Group for more than 17 years and oftentimes invited as a resource speaker in Fishery Law Enforcement Training to *Bantay Dagat* and coastal barangay officials nationwide, perceived that during the conduct of dialogue with them, problems are being encountered by the partnership between the Maritime Police, and Bantay Dagat that need to be addressed to have effective enforcement of fishery law. As a jumping point, the Researcher will conduct the study in the Province of Batangas where some obstacles observed include a lack of patrol boats and basic equipment to conduct monitoring and seaborne patrol; lack of trained coastal law enforcement units; and weak coordination between the law enforcers among others.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the methods by which the study was conducted and divided into specific areas; Research Design, Sources of Data, Data Gathering Instruments, Data Gathering Procedures, and Statistical Treatment of Data.

Method of Research

The study was basically descriptive and specifically of a descriptive-analytical nature. It gathered data from representative portions of the respondents- the Maritime Police, *the Bantay Dagat*, and residents of coastal barangays along Balayan Bay.

This is following the definition of Calderon and Gonzales (2014) which states that “descriptive research is a purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, trends, and cause-effect relationship and then making an adequate interpretation about such data”. Through this process, the problems in the partnership between the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* was revealed, and remedial measures were instituted.

The analysis was built from the responses of the respondent groups on their assessment, based on evidence, of the partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing from which data were tabulated and statistically analyzed using the appropriate statistical tests. The basis of the kind of data gathered was mainly on the items that were included in the instruments.

Given the nature of the partnership, a wide range of detailed interactions between the target groups were done by conducting key informants’ interviews. The latter procedure provided a qualitative detailed explanation that may not be captured by the items included in the questionnaire.

Population Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

The study was anchored on primary data that was generated from the three groups of respondents- the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* and residents of coastal barangays at Balayan Bay. The sizes of the sample respondents were based on accepted sampling procedures that were referred to as proportionate sizes based on population.

The Maritime Police comprised the personnel of the Maritime Police Station of Regional Maritime Unit 4A based in the province of Batangas. The two stations are located in Batangas City and Mabini. The focus of the study was the 7 coastal municipalities namely; Balayan, Calatagan, Lemery, Taal, San Luis, Bauan, and Mabini. Based on records, there were only Forty (40) assigned in the province of Batangas.

The *Bantay Dagat* members in Batangas were usually trained and deputized as fish wardens and contributes to eradicating illegal fishing methods such as the use of dynamite and cyanide. They also assist in raising the level of community awareness regarding environmental protection and fisheries management. Respondents from Bantay Dagat came from the above-mentioned coastal municipalities and they were selected because they were directly involved in fishery law enforcement.

Barangay residents came from the coastal barangays of the above municipalities and who's in their extent of performance of duties, have been exposed to situations where the partnership is evident and, at certain times and situations, have witnessed the same.

All respondents were chosen as representatives of their groups and individually selected therefrom based on randomization The total number of

respondents needed in the study was computed from the total population of the three groups using the 0.05 margin of error of Slovin's formula as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

n – Sample size

N – Population size

e – Desired margin of error

Table 4

Respondents of the Study

Category of Respondents	Total Population	Percentage	Sampling Size
Maritime Police	40	25.00	36
Bantay Dagat	50	31.25	45
Coastal Barangay Residents	70	43.75	59
TOTAL	160	100	140

Note: Adapted from Data Tabulation Results from Respondents.

Research Instrument

Following the construction of instruments, validation of the same was done based on the following; The first step in the validation process was the submission of the instrument to a group of experts in fishery law enforcement to check on the appropriateness and correctness of the statements therein. This step, while synchronizing the statements' construction to the standards of maritime law enforcement to ensure comprehension of the understanding by the respondents.

Conforming to the procedures of the selection of the final statements in the instruments, the Likert Scale standards were applied, thus;

1. The initial instrument was pretested to similar and parallel a group that

possesses almost-equal characteristics as the target of respondents.

2. Statements were ranked according to those ranked Very Effective/ Serious or Highly Recommended to Not Effective/Serious or Not recommended as the case may be.

Data Gathering Procedure

Questionnaire. A self-administered 3-Part questionnaire was used to gather primary data from the respondents. The questionnaire established the respondent groups assessment, the partnership perceived problems, and the list of recommendations.

Interview Study. An interview schedule was used for the key informants. The instruments were used to solicit qualitative data used to buttress the qualitative data gathered from the questionnaires and to provide a closer examination of the gaps that existed from the information that was gathered from the respondent. Key informants included the Chief of Regional Maritime Office 4A, the Chief of DENR Law Enforcement Division, and the Station Chief of the Batangas Maritime Police Station.

A pre-interview identification of the respondents was made after the identification of the coastal municipalities was completed and the samplings of these were satisfied. The procedure for the size determination per municipality/city was done using Slovin's formula using a sample error of 5%. The appropriate sampling procedure was stratified random sampling proportionate to size since proportions from the intended total sample were drawn from three sectors. Identification of specific respondents per municipality was done using random sampling drawn from a determined sampling frame. Specifically, the procedure subscribed to the following

sampling plan;

1. The total population of the respondent groups was taken to constitute 100%.
2. Regarding a 5% margin of error for sampling and by using Slovin's formula, the desired sample size was determined. Based on the pre-computed proportions of the respondent groups to the total population, the proportionate number of samples was determined.
3. The selection of the Bantay Dagat members was based on their three years of membership within their respective municipalities. This set the intended respondent has sufficient experience in fishery law enforcement.
4. From the computed sample sizes, the distribution of the number of respondents per area will likewise be determined based on the proportions of the sizes of the groups in the area; and
5. The final respondent selection was done using random sampling.

Based on the above, the identification of the specific respondents from all three sectors namely; the Maritime Police, Bantay Dagat, and coastal barangay residents, where questionnaires were distributed. All the responses were indicated based on the response options provided in the instrument.

To buttress the quantitative data from the questionnaires and to clarify unexpected responses that require further explanation, key informants were interviewed in all three sectors. The key informants included the Chief of the Regional Maritime Office 4A, the Barangay Dagat, and selected barangay officials from selected coastal barangays.

Secondary data were likewise derived from the Batangas Maritime Police Station of Region 4A and members of Bantay Dagat to further enrich the study's

database. The details and questions asked in the interview revolved around the same indicators outlined in the questionnaire.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical techniques were utilized to analyze and determine the reliability/validity of the data gathered. All the data collected were utilized and presented in tabular form, employing the following relevant tools applied as deemed necessary. The statistical tools used in this study were the percentage technique, average weighted mean, and chi-square.

Percentage is the itemized summation of the percentage of the frequency of each questionnaire based on the arithmetical percentage of the frequency distribution of the total number of responses. It is computed as follows:

$$P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100$$

Where:

P – Percentage

F – Frequency of responses

N – Total number of respondents

100 – Constant

Average Weighted Mean. This was used for the quantitative measurement of the responses on the items selected from a scale of 5 to 1, going higher points for the most degree and lesser points for the least degree. The weighted mean was composed of the accumulated responses to determine the local weight, which is typical of the respondents' responses using the formula.

$$X_w = \frac{\sum WX_n}{\sum W}$$

Where:

Xw – Weighted mean

WX – Sum of the product of the weighted frequencies

n – Total frequencies of the weighted frequencies

Σ – Summation

The Five-Point Rating Scale will be utilized. The quantifications of the ratings are as follows:

Scale	Limit	Quantitative Equivalent
5	4.20-5.00	Very Effective/Very Serious/Highly Recommended
4	3.40-4.19	Effective/Serious/Recommended
3	2.60-3.39	Moderately Effective/Moderately Serious/Moderately Recommended
2	1.80-2.59	Less Effective/Less Serious/Less Recommended
1	1.00- 1.79	Not Effective/ Not Serious/ Not Recommended.

IX. RESULTS, ANALYSIS, AND DISCUSSION

This chapter contains the results, analysis, and discussion of data based on the problems of the study.

The study focused on the partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay which specifically deal with three areas; innovative approaches, application of human resources, and coordinative activities. Responses on the specified areas were drawn from Maritime Police, *Bantay Dagat*, and residents of coastal barangay who are exposed to fishery law enforcement and observed the seaborne patrol operation of the Maritime Police, coastal barangay officials and *Bantay Dagat* in their respective areas.

1. Respondents' Assessment of the Partnership against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay

1.1 Innovative Approaches

Table 5 presents the data on the partnership of the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing in La Union province in terms of an Innovative Approach, designed as a new program for maritime law enforcement.

Among the five utilized indicators to assess the partnership, it appeared that the highest evidence in the assessment is found in indicator number 1 "Provide awareness campaign of the Adopt a Marine Protected Area Program to determine the focus of seaborne patrol operations." with AWM equivalent to 4.55 equivalent adjectival rating of "Highly Evident." It is the same indicator that showed HE among the other groups of respondents. This implies the importance of informing the

community about the bad effects of illegal fishing and penalties and prohibitions as provided under the Fishery Law particularly focusing on the law enforcement aspect. The result indicates that the partnership is serious about implementing the law by communicating to the community about the government's program on illegal fishing. Next in rank is the indicator "Inform the community about the fishery law enforcement program and bad effects of illegal fishing which garnered a GM value of 4.50 and also showed HE among the groups of respondents except for *Bantay Dagat*. This implies that the community is becoming more aware of the value of conserving marine protected areas as breeding grounds and fish sanctuaries. While indicators 5 and 4 – "Conduct seaborne patrol operation in the Balayan Bay province" and "Work hand in hand with LGUs in the campaign against illegal fishing" followed closely with AWM of 3.96 and 4.16 respectively.

Indicator 3 "Formulate and conduct Coastal Law Enforcement Training for Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat*" had the lowest WM value of 2.26 and the same was also reflected as the lowest among the three groups of respondents having the same "Less Evident" adjectival rating. This indicates that there is a need to have extensive and periodic training considered paramount and efficient in community policing. The group of respondents believed that Intensive training although initially costly in terms of money and time will eventually make the process more efficient because well-trained and efficient will share their knowledge with their colleagues.

It was observed that Maritime Police registered the highest OWM for all the indicators with 4.04 and an adjectival rating of "Highly Evident". This implies that the Maritime Police is supportive in achieving in eradicating the problems of illegal fishing through the introduction of innovative approaches such as training on fishery law enforcement and conduct of *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan*. Followed by Coastal

barangay officials and the *Bantay Dagat* and with OWM of 3.96 and 3.77 respectively. This clearly shows that both groups assessed aspects of partnership as growing evident and share a more positive stance towards its future strengthening.

Table 5

Respondents' Assessment of the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* Against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Innovative Approach

INDICATORS	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		Bantay Dagat		GRAND MEAN	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	AWM	VI
1. Inform the community about the fishery law enforcement program and the bad effects of illegal fishing.	4.44	HE	4.63	HE	4.42	HE	4.50	HE
2. Provide an awareness campaign of the Adopt a Marine Protected Area Program to determine the focus of seaborne patrol operations.	4.45	HE	4.64	HE	4.58	E	4.55	HE
3. Formulate and conduct Coastal Law Enforcement Training for Police and Bantay Dagat.	2.32	LE	2.05	LE	2.42	ME	2.26	LE
4. Work hand in hand with LGUs and NGOs in the campaign against illegal fishing.	4.08	E	4.36	HE	4.06	E	4.16	E
5. Conduct seaborne patrol operations in the coastal areas of Batangas province.	4.49	HE	4.52	HE	3.91	E	4.30	HE
OWM	3.96	E	4.04	E	3.77	E	3.92	E

Note: Adapted from Data Tabulation Results from Respondents, 2022.

Legend:

GM	Grand Mean	4.20- 5.00	Highly Evident (HE)
OWM	Overall Weighted Mean	3.40 - 4.19	Evident (E)
AWM	Average Weighted Mean	2.60- 3.39	Moderately Evident (ME)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	1.80- 2.59	Less Evident (LE)
WM	Weighted Mean	1.00- 1.79	Not Evident (NE)

1.2. Application of Human Resources

Assessment of Application of Human Resources is summarized in Table 6 which shows that there is one indicator that garnered “Highly Evident” as an adjectival rating and was recorded in indicator 5 - “Utilize available gas allocation and financial assistance as planned” with AWM of 4.25 in the first place followed by indicator 2 - “Employ additional police personnel and recruitment of *Bantay Dagat*.” With WM of 3.97 in the second place. While indicators 3 and 4 - “Show awareness by the PNP and LGU of the seaborne patrol equipment and communication device for the police and *Bantay Dagat*” and “Activate free legal assistance to the LGU to uplift their morale and welfare” were ranked fourth and third. This implies that the group of respondents perceived that a concrete indication of the success of the partnership is the commitment of the respective organizations to devote their resources to law enforcement programs. In addition legal assistance must be provided to protect the partnership from harassment by the offenders which will serve as a morale booster to the law enforcer.

Indicator number 1 garnered the lowest AWM of 2.73 with a verbal interpretation of LE is the “Exercise proper execution of Boarding Procedure by the Maritime Police, coastal barangay officials, and *Bantay Dagat*.” This is the same indicator that garnered the lowest mean values among the Maritime Police and Coastal barangay officials. The lowest observed indicator for the *Bantay Dagat* is “Show awareness by the PNP and LGU of seaborne patrol equipment communication device for the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials and *Bantay Dagat*.” This implies that skills involving the proper use of equipment are factors to be considered in a successful law enforcement program. Criminals device new ways of perpetrating their trade so viable alternative means must also be device by the

partnership in addressing such changes.

The lowest indicator “Exercise proper execution of the Boarding Procedure by the Police and *Bantay Dagat*” can be achieved by training. The entire group of respondents perceived that there is a need for skills enhancement on-boarding procedure considering the importance of joint seaborne patrol operations to complement the shortage of personnel of the Maritime Police and resources of *Bantay Dagat*. It was also observed by the group of respondents that there is a lack of coordination between the two groups because there is no training that will address the weakness of the partnership considering the importance of synchronizing movement that will further achieve a positive result if properly executed.

According to Sloan et al. (2002), training is crucial for the adoption of any significant change and is the foundation for how people and organizations respond to changes. A comprehensive training approach is essential in institutionalizing the philosophy and practice of community policing within a police agency. However, in designing training that meets the needs of the people who constitute end users of the training outcome, an effort must be made to solicit the input of the people.

Table 6

Respondents Assessment on the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* Against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Application of Human Resources

INDICATOR	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		Bantay Dagat		GRAND MEAN		
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	AWM	VI	
1. Exercise proper execution of the Boarding Procedure by the Police and Bantay Dagat personnel.	2.27	LE	1.9	LE	4.02	E	2.73	ME	
2. Employ additional police personnel and recruitment of Bantay Dagat with corresponding office orders.	3.83	ME	4.39	E	3.71	E	3.97	E	
3. Show awareness by the PNP and LGU of seaborne patrol equipment communication devices for the police and Bantay Dagat.	3.55	ME	3.58	ME	3.48	E	3.53	E	
4. Activate free legal assistance to the LGU to uplift their morale and welfare.	3.38	ME	3.44	ME	3.60	E	3.47	E	
5. Utilize available gas allocation and financial assistance as planned.	3.94	E	4.63	HE	4.20	HE	4.25	HE	
	OWM	3.39	ME	3.59	E	3.80	E	3.59	E

Note: Adapted from Data Tabulation Results from Respondents, 2022.

Legend:

GM	Grand Mean	4.20- 5.00	Highly Evident (HE)
OWM	Overall Weighted Mean	3.40 - 4.19	Evident (E)
AWM	Average Weighted Mean	2.60- 3.39	Moderately Evident (ME)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	1.80- 2.59	Less Evident (LE)
WM	Weighted Mean	1.00- 1.79	Not Evident (NE)

1.3 Coordinative Activities

Table 7 shows the assessment of the respondents on the partnership of the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay residents, and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay in terms of coordinative activities. It had an AWM of 4.00 and was interpreted as Evident. The indicator “Act on a timely report on the surveillance of illegal fishing activities for appropriate action” was Very Evident with a mean of 4.57. This implies that the community is supportive of giving information and they

can provide the police with insight into the specific crime within their neighborhood if the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* will respond to the report immediately. An increased level of community participation in crime reduction and prevention through the giving of information is an indication of a successful partnership.

Second in rank is the indicator “Enforce existing fishery laws/ordinances in the coastal areas without fear or favor” with AWM of 4.24. Tied in the third place are indicators “Maintain close coordination with the municipal/city government, BFAR and NGO by attending Peace and Order Council Meetings about fishery law enforcement” and “Coordinate with other law enforcement through information networking system about illegal fishing” both with AWM of 3.76 respectively. This indicates that some residents may appear unwilling to help the police because they do not trust them. In this regard, police must realize that sometimes the community seems helpless because it feels abandoned and would discover new strengths if only the police could make an effective alliance with important community elements.

The indicator “Execute joint affidavit of apprehension and file case against violators of fishery laws/ordinances” obtained the lowest AWM of 3.57. This indicates that the respondents observed that there is a need to file more cases against violators of illegal fishing considering the increasing trend of violations committed. Based on this result, community policing represents a drive that aspires to establish a partnership between the people and the police in addressing contemporary challenges to security such as social and physical disorder, crime, and fear of achieving overall life (Trojanowics and Bucqueroux, 1998).

Table 7

Respondents' Assessment of the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Coordinative Activities.

INDICATORS	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		Bantay Dagat		GRAND MEAN	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	AWM	VI
1. Act on a timely report on the surveillance of illegal fishing activities for appropriate action.	4.44	HE	4.94	HE	4.33	HE	4.57	HE
2. Enforce existing fishery laws/ordinances in the coastal areas without fear or favor.	3.74	E	4.83	HE	4.15	E	4.24	HE
3. Execute a joint affidavit of apprehension and file a case against violators of fishery laws/ordinances.	3.30	ME	4.61	HE	2.84	ME	3.58	E
4. Maintain close coordination with the municipal/city government, BFAR and NGO by attending Peace and Order Council Meetings about fishery law enforcement.	3.06	ME	4.61	HE	3.62	E	3.76	E
5. Coordinate with other law enforcement agencies through an information networking system about illegal fishing.	3.20	ME	4.33	HE	3.77	E	3.76	E
OWM	3.58	E	4.66	HE	3.77	E	4.00	E

Note: Adapted from Data Tabulation Results from Respondents, 2022.

Legend:

GM	Grand Mean	4.20- 5.00	Highly Evident (HE)
OWM	Overall Weighted Mean	3.40 - 4.19	Evident (E)
AWM	Average Weighted Mean	2.60- 3.39	Moderately Evident (ME)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	1.80- 2.59	Less Evident (LE)
WM	Weighted Mean	1.00- 1.79	Not Evident (NE)

1.4 Summary Results

The summary for all the indicators in the three areas of assessment is shown in Table 8. With the reflected weighted means indicated for each aspect, all respondents indicated them as “Evident” with GMW of 3.83. This shows that the partnership is felt and valued by the group of respondents. The Maritime Police had the highest grand weighted mean value for all areas at 4.09. Moreover, the Maritime Police showed the highest mean value for Coordinative Activities at 4.66 and the lowest for the Application of Human Resources at 3.59. This implied that the Police observed that the new programs introduced by Maritime Group were gaining momentum while there is still a need for additional manpower and equipment in terms of the Application of Human Resources. On the other hand, the *Bantay Dagat* had the same observation for the highest mean for the Application of Human Resources. Likewise, coastal barangay residents had the same evaluation with the Innovative Approaches at 3.96. Followed by Coordinative Activities at 3.58 and Application of Human Resources at 3.39. It should be noted that the highest means among the three groups are varied and their assessments for pieces of evidence of the partnership are divergent. Consistent with all areas of assessment and among the three groups, the value shows marked impressions in the “Evident category.” However, improvements are open and can be further enhanced especially in the Application of Human Resources where the lowest grand mean value of 3.59 is observed.

Generally speaking, Skolmick and Bayley (2008) concluded that viewing community policing standards around the world will identify that commonality can be an approach to community policing. These common attributes are: (a) a growing shift to” community-based crime prevention” all over the world through the use of citizen

education, neighborhood watch, and similar techniques, as opposed to relying on police patrol to prevent crime. (b) a change in direction from an emergency response (chasing calls) to proactive such as foot patrol, (c) increased accountability in the police towards the citizen and community at large.

Table 8

Summary Assessment on the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay.

VARIABLES	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		Bantay Dagat		GRAND MEAN	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	OWM	VI
1 Innovative Approach	3.96	E	4.04	E	3.77	E	3.92	E
2 Application of Human Resources	3.39	ME	3.59	E	3.80	E	3.59	E
3 Coordinative Activities	3.58	E	4.66	HE	3.77	E	4.00	E
GWM	3.64	E	4.09	E	3.78	E	3.83	E

Note: Adapted from Data Tabulation Results from Respondents, 2022.

Legend:

GM	Grand Mean	4.20- 5.00	Highly Evident (HE)
OWM	Overall Weighted Mean	3.40 - 4.19	Evident (E)
AWM	Average Weighted Mean	2.60- 3.39	Moderately Evident (ME)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	1.80- 2.59	Less Evident (LE)
WM	Weighted Mean	1.00- 1.79	Not Evident (NE)

2. Respondents' Assessment of the Problems encountered by the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* against Illegal fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Innovative Approach.

Table 9 displays the problems encountered in the partnership of the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing in the coastal areas of La Union province in terms of innovative approaches. The indicator "Failure of the PNP to formulate and conduct Coastal Law Enforcement Training to the Police, Coastal barangay officials and *Bantay Dagat* due to the non-inclusion to the Annual Training Program" obtained the highest AWM of 4.11 interpreted as Serious. This implied that the group of respondents observed that there is no periodic training being conducted to enhance the skill of the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and *Bantay Dagat* and they valued the importance of training as part and parcel of an effective law enforcement program. Next in rank are indicators; "Lack of commitment by the PNP and LGU to give awards and commendation to Police and *Bantay Dagat* who exhibit dedication to service"; "Irregular conduct of joint seaborne patrol operations due to absence of Fishery Law Enforcement Team"; and "Unable to identify the Marine Protected Areas by the police and *Bantay Dagat* to determine the focus of their seaborne patrol operations" with AWM of 3.55; 3.01 and 2.64 respectively.

The indicator "Lack of interest of the police, Coastal barangay officials and *Bantay Dagat* to conduct *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan* to the community about the bad effects of illegal fishing" obtained the lowest AWM of 2.50. This indicates that information campaigns on the effects of illegal fishing were being undertaken and recognized by the respondents as one of the tools for effective law enforcement. This shows that there is a need to sustain the conduct of this activity that will serve

as a forum for a dialogue between the law enforcers and the community. It will also provide an exchange of information to suggest and recommend measures to address the problems of illegal fishing that will send a warning to the violators that the partnership with the support of the community is serious in enforcing the fishery law.

Relatively, the reason for the emergence of community-oriented policing is that often citizens watch crime take place in their community without reporting because they do not want to “get involved” or they do not trust the police. According to George L. Kelling, (2008). If the police realize that they exist for the people and without them, they cannot prevent crime. The overarching goal of community-oriented policing should be for the police to become partners with the community and empower them so that they can make their neighborhoods safer (Trojanowics, 2011). The main goal of community policing is to improve the crime control capacities of the police by creating an effective working relationship between the community and the police (Moore and Trojanowics, 2008). Community policing invites citizens to collaborate with the people to establish a community-specific crime-fighting agenda (Weinstein, 2008). This policy also utilizes problem-solving techniques, encouraging police to seek creative, pro-active solutions to solve community problems (Moore and Trojanowics, 2008).

Table 9

Problems Encountered by the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Innovative Approach.

INDICATORS	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		Bantay Dagat		GRAND MEAN	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	AWM	VI
1. Lack of interest of the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and Bantay Dagat to conduct Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan to the community about the bad effects of illegal fishing.	2.54	LS	2.41	LS	2.55	MS	2.50	MS
2. Unable to identify the Marine Protected Areas by the police and Bantay Dagat to determine the focus of their seaborne patrol operations.	3.54	S	1.97	LS	2.42	MS	2.64	MS
3. Failure of the PNP to formulate and conduct Coastal Law Enforcement Training for the Maritime Police, Barangay Police, and Bantay Dagat due to the non-inclusion of the Annual Training Program.	4.13	S	4.50	VS	3.73	S	4.11	S
4. Lack of commitment by the PNP and LGU to give awards and commendations to the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and Bantay Dagat who exhibit dedication to service.	3.67	S	3.80	S	3.20	MS	3.55	S
5. Irregular conduct of joint seaborne patrol operations due to the absence of the Fishery Law Enforcement Team.	3.20	MS	3.11	MS	2.73	MS	3.01	MS
OWM	3.41	MS	3.15	MS	2.93	MS	3.16	MS

Note: Adapted from Data Tabulation Results from Respondents, 2022.

Legend:

WM	Weighted Mean	4.20- 5.00	Very Serious (VS)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	3.40- 4.19	Serious (S)
AWM	Average Weighted Mean	2.60-3.39	Moderately Serious (MS)
OWM	Overall Weighted Mean	1.80- 2.59	Less Serious (S)
GM	Grand Mean	1.00- 1.79	Not Serious (NS)

2.1. Application of Human Resources

Table 10 shows the problems encountered by the partnership of the Maritime Police, coastal barangay officials, and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing in the coastal areas of La Union province in terms of the application of human resources. The OWM was Moderately Serious with a mean of 2.77 and all indicators in AWM had the same evaluation. The indicator “Insufficient knowledge of the police and *Bantay Dagat* in the conduct of boarding procedure” garnered the highest AWM of 3.30. This indicates that joint seaborne patrol operation by the Maritime Police, coastal barangay residents, and *Bantay Dagat* is not visible because the boarding procedure involves a synchronized movement that entails proper execution through proper training. This also shows that there is a lack of coordination in the enforcement of fishery laws between the Maritime Police, coastal barangay officials, and *Bantay Dagat*. Next in rank were indicators “Failure by the PNP and LGU to provide additional seaborne patrol equipment and communication device”; “Limited gas allocation provided by the PNP and LGU to police and *Bantay Dagat*” and “No legal assistance provided by the PNP and LGU to the police and *Bantay Dagat*” with AWM of 2.70; 2.68 and 2.66.

The indicator “Lack of police personnel and *Bantay Dagat* deployed in the coastal areas” obtained the lowest AWM of 2.52. This implied that there is a sufficient number of law enforcers to perform their duties as guardians of the maritime environment if complemented by *Bantay Dagat* and coastal barangay officials which means that manpower is not the problem but the group of respondents observed that it lies in training and lack of equipment.

Table 10

Problems Encountered by the Partnership Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Application of Human Resources.

INDICATORS	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		<i>Bantay Dagat</i>		GRAND MEAN		
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	AWM	VI	
1. Insufficient knowledge of the police and Bantay Dagat in the conduct of the Boarding Procedure.	1.57	NS	4.00	S	4.33	VS	3.30	MS	
2. Lack of police personnel and Bantay Dagat deployed in the coastal areas.	2.17	LS	2.58	MS	2.80	MS	2.52	MS	
3. Failure by the PNP and LGU to provide additional seaborne patrol equipment and communication device.	2.23	MS	3.00	MS	2.88	MS	2.70	MS	
4. No legal assistance was provided by the PNP and LGU to the police and Bantay Dagat.	2.08	LS	2.69	MS	3.28	MS	2.66	MS	
5. Limited gas allocation provided by the PNP and LGU to police and Bantay Dagat.	2.56	MS	2.77	MS	2.71	MS	2.68	MS	
	OWM	2.12	LS	3.00	MS	3.20	MS	2.77	MS

Note: Adapted from Data Tabulation Results from Respondents, 2022.

Legend:

WM	Weighted Mean	4.20- 5.00	Very Serious (VS)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	3.40- 4.19	Serious (S)
AWM	Average Weighted Mean	2.60-3.39	Moderately Serious (MS)
OWM	Overall Weighted Mean	1.80- 2.59	Less Serious (S)
GM	Grand Mean	1.00- 1.79	Not Serious (NS)

2.2. Coordinative Activities

Table 11 affirmed the problems encountered in the partnership of the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay residents, and Bantay Dagat against illegal fishing at Balayan Bay in terms of the application of coordinative activities. It had an overall mean of 2.28 interpreted as Less Serious. The indicator “Delay in rendering report of illegal fishing activities by the police and *Bantay Dagat* due to inadequacy of communication device” garnered the highest AWM of 2.54 interpreted as Less Serious. This implied that communication is an indispensable tool in every law enforcement program and there must be open communication lines guaranteed by the issuance of the communication device. Technology plays an important role in community partnership because it helps agencies identify and analyze problems which can lead to long-term solutions (Hickman & Reaves, 2005). Partnerships tend to work better when there is a common goal in sharing data such as solving a specific, local crime problem. To be an effective technological device to be used by all of the contributing agencies (Boba et al., 2009).

Next in rank were indicators “Unwillingness of the police and Bantay Dagat to enforce fishery laws/ordinances due to lack of commitment and dedication;” “Lack of interest by the police and Bantay Dagat to file cases due to fear of counter-charge against them;” and Uncooperative attitude of the police and Bantay Dagat to support the anti-illegal fishing program of city/municipal government, BFAR, and NGO with AMW of 2.24, 2.19, and 14. This can be attributed to the fact that the success of a positive-community partnership, as with most community-oriented initiatives, hinges on the involvement of each stakeholder. This includes, but is not limited to businesses, schools, churches, city agencies, and individual community members. Research also suggests an important step when forming a community-based

partnership is to take into account cultural influences within the community (Payne & Button, 2009).

The indicator “Lack of coordination between the police and Bantay Dagat in the information networking with other law enforcement agencies” obtained the lowest AWM of 2.14. This shows that active networking of the intelligence community in coastal areas of Balayan Bay although lacking in communication devices needed to disseminate such vital information.

To build a relationship, police can also offer opportunities to expose criminal justice students to COP practices, participate in activities that encourage trust between the police and residents, and police providing a clear message that their neighborhood does not accept violence as a norm (Mazerolle, Wickes, & McBroom, 2010). Some police agencies give patrol officers permanent assignments to specific geographic areas so that they can involve in community organizations, establish ongoing communications with other agencies, and orchestrate opportunities for police-community interactions (Chappel, 2009).

Table 11

Problems Encountered by the Partnership of the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Coordinative Activities.

INDICATORS	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		<i>Bantay Dagat</i>		GRAND MEAN	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	AWM	VI
1. Delay in rendering reports of illegal fishing activities by the police and Bantay Dagat due to inadequacy of communication devices.	2.38	LS	2.19	LS	3.06	MS	2.54	LS
2. Unwillingness of the police and Bantay Dagat to enforce fishery laws/ordinances due to lack of	2.25	LS	2.02	LS	2.53	LS	2.26	LS

INDICATORS	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		<i>Bantay Dagat</i>		GRAND MEAN	
commitment and dedication.								
3. Lack of interest by the police and Bantay Dagat to file cases due to fear of counter-charge against them.	2.19	LS	1.88	LS	2.64	MS	2.24	LS
4. Uncooperative attitude of the police and Bantay Dagat to support the anti-illegal fishing program of city/municipal government, BFAR and NGO.	2.03	LS	1.75	LS	2.80	MS	2.19	LS
5. Lack of coordination between the police and Bantay Dagat in the information networking with other law enforcement agencies.	1.83	LS	1.86	LS	2.73	MS	2.14	LS
OWM	2.14	LS	1.94	LS	2.75	MS	2.28	LS

Note: Adapted from Data Tabulation Results from Respondents, 2022.

Legend:

WM	Weighted Mean	4.20- 5.00	Very Serious (VS)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	3.40- 4.19	Serious (S)
AWM	Average Weighted Mean	2.60-3.39	Moderately Serious (MS)
OWM	Overall Weighted Mean	1.80- 2.59	Less Serious (S)
GM	Grand Mean	1.00- 1.79	Not Serious (N)

2.3. Summary Results

The summary table for all the problems identified by the respondent groups for the partnership is concisely shown with each of the weighted means computed in Table 12. While the mean values for all aspects do not vary much among the group of respondents, they consider more problems in the Innovative Approach with a weighted mean of 3.15. This implied that the respondent is still adjusting to the new program approach being implemented by the partnership and they are not feeling the effects of such innovations. Next in rank is the Application of Human Resources with a weighted mean of 2.77 which shows that the respondents valued the importance of communication, however, lack of equipment is hindering the successful dissemination of the same. Lastly, the Coordinative Activities obtained the lowest OWM among the group of respondents with a mean of 2.28 which implied that coordination among the partnership and they need only to synchronize their

movement through training to further enhance it. The three groups of respondents assessed the problem to be in the middle ground although relatively within the manageable level with a focus on the problem of communication to enhance the human resources in the campaign against illegal fishing.

The above analysis indicates that community policing calls for long-term commitment and it is not a quick fix. Achieving ongoing partnerships with the community to eradicate the underlying causes of crime will take an innovative approach, application of human resources, and coordinative resources. A concrete indication of community policing success is the commitment of community policing resources devoted to crime reduction efforts. Active consultation and financial participation by public and private agencies and the business community will demonstrate that community partnership efforts are working. An analysis of the nature of calls for police service requiring assistance will indicate that the strategy is working. Agencies that can successfully realign their resources by forming community partnerships will be able to make community policing more efficient and cost-effective.

Table 12

Summary Assessment on the Problem Encountered by the Partnership against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay

VARIABLES	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		<i>Bantay Dagat</i>		GRAND MEAN	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	OWM	VI
1 Innovative Approaches	3.41	S	3.16	MS	2.93	MS	3.15	MS
2 Application of Human Resources	2.12	LS	3.00	MS	3.20	MS	2.77	MS

VARIABLES	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		<i>Bantay Dagat</i>		GRAND MEAN	
	3 Coordinative Activities	2.14	LS	1.94	LS	2.75	MS	2.28
GWM	2.55	LS	2.70	MS	2.96	MS	2.73	MS

Note: Adapted from Data Tabulation Results from Respondents, 2022.

Legend:

WM	Weighted Mean	4.20- 5.00	Very Serious (VS)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	3.40- 4.19	Serious (S)
AWM	Average Weighted Mean	2.60-3.39	Moderately Serious (MS)
OWM	Overall Weighted Mean	1.80- 2.59	Less Serious (S)
GM	Grand Mean	1.00- 1.79	Not Serious (N)

3. Respondents' Assessment of the Proposed Measures for the Problems Encountered by the Partnership against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay.

3.1. Innovative Approach

Table 13 showed the proposed measures to address the problems encountered by the partnership of Maritime Police, coastal barangay residents, and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing at Balayan Bay in terms of the Innovative Approach. It had an overall mean of 3.98 and was interpreted as Recommended. All indicators were also recommended as recorded by the three groups of respondents.

The indicator "Monthly conduct of *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan* to serve as community awareness on the bad effects of illegal fishing" obtained the highest AWM 4.20. This is a concrete indication that the success of partnership can be achieved through active consultation and participation of the community that will demonstrate that their combine efforts are working and gearing towards effective law enforcement programs. Next in rank were indicators "Conduct of quarterly Coastal Law Enforcement Training to police and *Bantay Dagat*," "Giving awards and recognition by the PNP and *Bantay Dagat* during special occasions for exemplary service," and "Creation of Fishery Law Enforcement Team that provides lectures in

fishery laws” with AMW of 4.02; 4.01. and 3.91 respectively. This only proves that this kind of incentive motivates the partnership to solve the problems that affect the security and harmony of the community. With high morale and greater job satisfaction, the partnership will more effectively mobilize the community. If they are highly motivated, given the necessary support, and appropriately rewarded for their efforts then the job satisfaction they experience will make community policing strategy a success.

The indicator “Installation of bouy marker on the marine protected areas to determine the focus of seaborne patrol operation” obtained the lowest AWM of 3.85 which indicates that these bouy markers were already in place and served as visible aid during law enforcement operations.

Table 13

Proposed Measures to Enhance the Partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in Terms of Innovative Approach

INDICATORS	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		<i>Bantay Dagat</i>		GRAND MEAN	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	AWM	VI
1. Monthly conduct of Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan to serve as community awareness on the bad effects of illegal fishing.	3.97		R 4.08	R	4.55	HR	4.20	HR
2. Installation of buoy markers on the marine protected areas to determine the focus of seaborne patrol operation.	4.03		R 3.94	R	3.57	R	3.85	R
3. Conduct quarterly Coastal Law Enforcement Training for Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and Bantay Dagat.	4.14		R 3.77	R	4.15	R	4.02	R

INDICATORS	Coastal barangay officials	Maritime Police	<i>Bantay Dagat</i>	GRAND MEAN
4. Giving awards and recognition by the PNP and LGU to Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and Bantay Dagat during special occasions for exemplary service.	4.20	R 4.19	R 3.66	R 4.01
5. Creation of a Fishery Law Enforcement Team composed of Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and Bantay Dagat that provides lectures on fishery laws.	3.76	R 4.02	R 3.93	R 3.91
OWM	3.96	R 4.00	R 3.97	R 3.98

Note: Regional Maritime Police Office 4-A Accomplishment Report, 2022.

Legend:

WM	Weighted Mean	4.20- 5.00	Highly Recommended (HR)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	3.40- 4.19	Recommended (R)
AWM	Average Weighted Mean	2.60-3.39	Moderately Recommended (MR)
OWM	Overall Weighted Mean	1.80- 2.59	Less Recommended (LR)
GM	Grand Mean	1.00- 1.79	Not Recommended (NR)

3.2. Application of Human Resources

Table 14 shows the proposed measures to address the problems encountered by the partnership of Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing in the coastal areas of La Union province in terms of the Application of Human Resources. The overall mean was 4.15 interpreted as Recommended. The indicator “Actual demonstration of Boarding Procedure during the conduct of training for the police and *Bantay Dagat*” obtained the highest AWM of 4.39 interpreted as Highly Recommended. Next in rank are indicators “Conduct training to the PNP and Bantay Dagat on the proper handling of the issued seaborne patrol equipment and communication device” with AMW of 4.37; Conduct training for the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and *Bantay Dagat* on the proper handling of the issued seaborne patrol equipment and communication device with AMW of and Creation of Technical Working Group

composed of PNP, LGU, and NGO and discuss the status of logistical support concerning this program. The above analysis only proved that training and communication play an important role in the partnership. This synergy of the partnership on training and proper communication.

It is quite evident that the prospects are good because the philosophy of community policing is being advanced as the new policing system for the twenty-first century (Palmiotto, 2011). He further identified certain factors that will have a greater influence on the future development of community policing initiatives. The first point raised has to do with the acknowledged growing influence by people of the insecurity around them. New strategies are being adapted by community members on how to secure their neighborhood to have peace of mind and good life Palmiotto (2011).

Table 14

Proposed Measures to Enhance the Partnership against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in terms of Application of Human Resources

INDICATORS	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		<i>Bantay Dagat</i>		GRAND MEAN	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	AWM	VI
1. Actual demonstration of boarding procedure during the conduct of training for the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and <i>Bantay Dagat</i> .	4.42	R	4.19	HR	4.55	HR	4.39	HR
2. Conduct a series of meetings on the disadvantages of illegal fishing in identified areas.	4.29	HR	4.41	HR	4.08	R	4.26	HR
3. Conduct training for the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and <i>Bantay Dagat</i> on the proper handling of the issued seaborne patrol equipment and communication	4.49	HR	4.39	HR	4.22	R	4.37	HR

INDICATORS	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		<i>Bantay Dagat</i>		GRAND MEAN	
device.								
4. Orient the LGU on the free legal assistance program.	3.76	R	3.92	R	3.44	R	3.69	R
5. Creation of a Technical Working Group composed of representatives from PNP, LGU, and NGO and discuss the status of logistical support with this program.	4.12	R	4.39	HR	3.66	R	4.06	R
OWM	4.22	R	4.26	HR	3.99	R	4.15	R

Note: Adapted from Data Tabulation Results from Respondents, 2022.

Legend:

WM	Weighted Mean	4.20- 5.00	Highly Recommended (HR)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	3.40- 4.19	Recommended (R)
AWM	Average Weighted Mean	2.60-3.39	Moderately Recommended (MR)
OWM	Overall Weighted Mean	1.80- 2.59	Less Recommended (LR)
GM	Grand Mean	1.00- 1.79	Not Recommended (NR)

3.3. Coordinative Activities

Table 15 explained the measures that can be proposed to address the problems encountered by the partnership of Maritime Police, and Bantay Dagat against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay in terms of coordinative activities. Its interpretation was Recommended with an OWM of 4.12. The indicator, “PNP to provide cellphones to the police and Bantay Dagat in coordination with the SMART in connection with OPLAN DALOY program” obtained the highest AWM of 4.44 This only shows that technology is considered as best practice in community policing. The use of cell phones enables the partnership to share vital information, receive feedback and interact with each other. Next in rank are indicators “Conduct lecture on the Rules on Criminal Procedure and Rules of Engagement to the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and Bantay Dagat”; Include in the *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan* about the fishery law enforcement program of the PNP, LGU, and BFAR” and “Conduct seminar on basic intelligence and invite other law enforcement intelligence community.

The indicator “Conduct lecture on Arrest, Search, and Seizure to Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials and Bantay Dagat to avoid the bungling of the case” obtained the lowest AWM of 3.63. This implied that the groups of respondents are aware that most cases filed were oftentimes dismissed due to technicalities involving the arrest and search warrants. Training on this aspect is crucial for an effective law enforcement strategy. It is crucial for the adoption of any significant change and is the foundation for how people and organizations respond to changes. A comprehensive training approach is essential in institutionalizing the philosophy and practice of community policing within a police agency.

Table 15

Proposed Measures to Enhance the Partnership of Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay in terms of Coordinative Activities

INDICATORS	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		<i>Bantay Dagat</i>		GRAND MEAN	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	AWM	VI
1. PNP to provide cellphones to the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and Bantay Dagat in coordination with the SMART in connection with OPLAN DALOY program.	4.59	HR	4.47	HR	4.26	HR	4.44	HR
2. Conduct a lecture on the Rules on Criminal Procedure and Rules of Engagement to the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and Bantay Dagat.	4.19	R	4.33	HR	4.18	R	4.23	HR
3. Conduct of lecture on Arrest, Search, and Seizure to the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and Bantay Dagat to avoid the bungling of the case.	4.22	HR	2.80	LR	3.87	R	3.63	R

INDICATORS	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		<i>Bantay Dagat</i>		GRAND MEAN	
4. Include in the <i>Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan</i> about the fishery law enforcement program of the PNP, LGU and BFAR.	4.36	HR	4.17	R	4.08	R	4.20	R
5. Conduct a seminar on basic intelligence and invite other law enforcement intelligence communities.	4.41	HR	4.14	R	3.73	R	4.09	R
OWM	4.35	HR	3.98	R	4.02	R	4.12	R

Note: Adapted from Data Tabulation Results from Respondents, 2022.

Legend:

WM	Weighted Mean	4.20- 5.00	Highly Recommended (HR)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	3.40- 4.19	Recommended (R)
AWM	Average Weighted Mean	2.60-3.39	Moderately Recommended (MR)
OWM	Overall Weighted Mean	1.80- 2.59	Less Recommended (LR)
GM	Grand Mean	1.00- 1.79	Not Recommended (NR)

3.4. Summary Results

Table 16 presents the summary of the three respondent groups about proposed measures to enhance the partnership of the Maritime Police, coastal barangay residents, and Bantay Dagat in coordinative activities.

The Coastal barangay officials feel that the strongest enhancement must be with measures in Coordinative Activities with a mean value of 4.35 and the lowest is Innovative Approach with 3.96. The Maritime Police otherwise believed that the enhancement must be in Application of Human Resources with 4.39 and the least is also the Coordinated Activities with a mean value of 3.98. The Bantay Dagat focused on the Coordinative Activities at 4.12 and the least is the innovative approach at 3.98.

The above analysis implies that the group of respondents has different perceptions in dealing with crime solutions. However, this only shows that law enforcement is a goal that cannot be accomplished by one person, program, or strategy but through the collaboration of inputs of the involved agencies. Comparing

the overall weighted mean values between the respondent groups, the Coastal barangay residents appear to be adamant about the enhancement of measures with a high mean value of 4.18. While the other 2 groups follow very closely with 4.12 and 3.88 respectively. Coordinative Activities was rated by the three groups of the respondent the highest at 4.12. The grand mean of 4.07 classified as “Recommended” strongly implies that the enhancement of the partnership is never to be neglected and corresponding measures are proposed. The variation may be deemed important in the perceived enhancement, which implies where a degree of weakness lies.

Table 16

Summary Assessment of the Proposed Measures to Enhance the Partnership against Illegal Fishing in Balayan Bay

VARIABLES	Coastal barangay officials		Maritime Police		Bantay Dagat		GRAND MEAN	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	OWM	VI
1 Innovative Approaches	3.96	R	4.00	R	3.97	R	3.98	R
2 Application of Human Resources	4.22	R	4.39	HR	3.66	R	4.09	R
3 Coordinative Activities	4.35	HR	3.98	R	4.02	R	4.12	R
GWM	4.18	R	4.12	R	3.88	R	4.07	R

Note: Adapted from Data Tabulation Results from Respondents, 2022.

Legend:

WM	Weighted Mean	4.20- 5.00	Highly Recommended (HR)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	3.40- 4.19	Recommended (R)
AWM	Average Weighted Mean	2.60-3.39	Moderately Recommended (MR)
OWM	Overall Weighted Mean	1.80- 2.59	Less Recommended (LR)
GM	Grand Mean	1.00- 1.79	Not Recommended (NR)

4. Interview Results and Analysis

The survey conducted among the three groups provided the basis for the analysis of the problems posited for the study based on selected indicators. However, other than the survey, interviews of persons considered as the informants were conducted to further buttress the qualitative information, interviews were done on representatives of the respondents All were based in the Province of Batangas where the study was conducted. *Bantay Dagat* in many of the coastal municipalities stated that many of them do not have the proper training to respond to crimes although they are usually the first responders against illegal fishing in the coastal areas.

A veteran *Bantay Dagat* who conceal his identity said that, over the years, his variety of experiences hone his skills on how to handle illegal fishing operations before the arrival of the Maritime Police who are more trained to handle the situations. However, he grimaces over the fact that the limited knowledge of fishery law enforcement still poses a lot of opportunities for errors that must and should be avoided.

Mostly, *Bantay Dagat* does not conceal the fact that they still lack equipment and materials, and sometimes these resources came from their own and other concerned groups. Admittedly, much of what they possess is inadequate and mostly inappropriate. They hope that beyond the supply of the desired training component, they should be given the provision of materials that would enhance their efficiency and job performance. *Bantay Dagat* appreciates the skills they have acquired over practice and exposure but formal training is a priority. Some procedures are known and their importance is emphasized. But they underscore the lack of materials to institute them continues to prevent them from adhering to the requirements.

The Maritime Police have likewise expressed concerns over coordination and the limited availability of communication lines that will enhance better coordination. Police stated, that in some instances, the time-lapse and the first response of the *Bantay Dagat* caused the violators of fishery law to escape. The Maritime Police need the assistance of the *Bantay Dagat* because not every municipality of Batangas has Maritime Police Station. The only station is located in Mabini, Batangas. Therefore, the presence of *Bantay Dagat* in other coastal municipalities is indispensable. With the rising incidents of illegal fishing in Balayan Bay, the Maritime Police desire to synchronize their operations and procedures with *Bantay Dagat*.

PCOL GREG TOGONON, Chief of the Regional Maritime Office 4A based at Lucena, Quezon City, noticed the willingness of the *Bantay Dagat* to assist in the enforcement of fishery law enforcement. However, they are not properly trained and equipped to effectively perform the job. Hence, he urgently proposed the conduct of training in all aspects of fishery law enforcement.

Dr. Rogelio Demelletes, DENR Chief of Law Enforcement and *Bantay Dagat* Coordinator, emphasized that the partnership is most crucial as the need to engage people in securing the coastal environment. He mentioned that it is not even the care for a response but the concern for prevention. He insisted that the desired partnership is yet most wanting in many areas and aspects. It is not to blame any of the parties involved in responding to crime but they say it is the training that exhibits the gaps in efficiency. He even mentioned this to be “frustrating” in some experiences where poor training in some cases.

Despite this predicament, the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* believed they are partners in the hope of instituting certain degrees of order and inviting

greater multi-sector involvement in the work. LGUs must support the partnership and engage civic organizations and the entire civil society in the concern.

LGU involvement, including the Barangays, is indispensable since the objectives of the partnership lie parallel to the concern of LGU performance-the establishment of a safe and secure maritime environment. Civil society, NGOs state is a viable partner that must likewise be aggressively engaged-financial and materials support, conduct and sponsorship of training, or even a potential responding team in the long run.

PCapt Benito Siddayao, Chief of Batangas Maritime Police Station, mentioned that in any way stress the importance of Bantay Dagat in emergency response. He said that the Bantay Dagat is more than willing to help. However, considering the current arrangements, of the Bantay Dagat, he seeks additional training for the people to effectively perform their duties and responsibilities.

5. Proposed Action Plan

The Coastal Law Enforcement Training (FLET) Program of Instruction (POI) for the enhancement of the partnership of the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay, and *Bantay Dagat* against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay is based on the results of the study and interviews. The indicators with the lowest mean values for the assessment and the indicators with the highest mean values for the problems encountered and proposed measures were also considered to be incorporated into the proposed action plan.

In the assessment, the least observed variable in the partnership of the Maritime Police, Coastal barangay officials, and *Bantay Dagat* in terms of Innovative Approach is the Formulation and conduct of Coastal Law Enforcement Training for

the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat*. In terms of the Application of Human Resources, the indicator that is least observed in the partnership is “Exercise proper execution of the Boarding Procedure by the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* personnel.” While in the area of Coordinative Activities, the least evident indicator is “Coordinate with other law enforcement agencies through information networking systems about illegal fishing.”

On the other hand, “Failure of the PNP to formulate and conduct Coastal Law Enforcement Training to the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* due to the non-inclusion to the Annual Training Program,” “Irregular conduct of joint seaborne patrol operations due to absence of Fishery Law Enforcement Team,” and “Lack of interest of the police and *Bantay Dagat* to conduct *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan* to the community about the bad effects of illegal fishing” were assessed by the three groups of respondents the highest from the among the serious problems in Innovative Approach thus highly recommended the following; in terms of innovative approach, “Monthly conduct of *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan* to serve as community awareness on the bad effects of illegal fishing;” “Creation of Fishery Law Enforcement Team composed of police and *Bantay Dagat* that provides lecture in fishery laws;” and Giving awards and recognition by the PNP and LGU to police and *Bantay Dagat* during special occasions for exemplary service.

In terms of the Application of Human Resources, Conduct training for the PNP and *Bantay Dagat* on the proper handling of the issued seaborne patrol equipment and communication device. While in terms of Coordinative Activities, it was highly recommended to Conduct a lecture on the Rules of Criminal Procedure and Rules of Engagement to the police and *Bantay Dagat* and Conduct of lecture on Arrest, Search, and Seizure to police and *Bantay Dagat* to avoid the bungling of the

case.

Based on the research findings, the first aspect of the enhancement program would be the formulation of the Program of Instruction (POI) of the Fishery Law Enforcement for both the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* to enhance their knowledge about RA 10651 or the fishery laws, Boarding Procedure, Rules of Engagement, Arrest, Search and Seizure; Basic Intelligence and Investigation among others. Initially, this program of instruction shall be intended for the potential trainers to reecho the training to other coastal municipalities of Batangas. The main objective of the training is to educate the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* to thoroughly understand their roles and for the latter to able to perform their duties as a force multiplier of the PNP effectively.

In terms of coordinative activities, the topic of arrest, search and seizure, and Rules of Engagement shall be included in the training module and highlight its significance and advantages not only in boosting crime efficiency but particularly for the *Bantay Dagat* to be well informed on the job of a law enforcer.

X. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

The chapter presents the outcome of the study, its recommendations, and its conclusion. All the facts included herein are based on the procedures and methodology adopted in the entire study and the data presented in the preceding chapter.

Findings

The study's major highlights are herewith outlined based on the prescribed procedures and methods;

5.1.1. Assessment of the partnership between the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* is Effective.

5.1.1.1. In the Innovative Approach area, it had an OWM with a verbal interpretation of 3.92 and interpreted as Evident. The Indicator "Inform the community about fishery law enforcement program and the bad effects of illegal fishing" obtained the highest AWM of 4.55. While the indicator "Formulate and conduct Coastal Law Enforcement Training for the Maritime Police, coastal barangay officials and *Bantay Dagat*" obtained the lowest AWM of 2.20 interpreted as Less Evident.

5.1.1.2. The area of Application of Human Resources had an OWM of 3.59 and was interpreted as Evident. The indicator "Utilize available gas allocation and financial assistance as planned" had the highest AWM of 4.25 and was interpreted as Highly Evident. On the other hand, the indicator: "Exercise proper execution of the Boarding Procedure by the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* personnel" obtained the lowest AWM of 2.73 interpreted as Moderately Evident.

5.1.1.3. The area of Coordinative Activities had an OWM of 4.00 and was interpreted as Evident. The indicator “Act on a timely report on the surveillance of illegal fishing activities for appropriate action” obtained the highest AWM interpreted as Highly Evident with a mean of 4.57. On the other hand, the indicator “Execute joint affidavit of apprehension and file case against violators of fishery laws/ordinances” obtained the lowest AWM of 2.89 interpreted as Moderately Evident.

5.1.2. All respondent groups have indicated various degrees of seriousness for the apparent problems encountered by the partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* in three areas.

5.1.2.1. The area of Innovative Approaches had an overall mean of 3.16 and was interpreted as Moderately Serious. The indicator “Failure of the PNP to formulate and conduct coastal Law Enforcement Training to the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* due to the non-inclusion to the Annual Training Program” obtained the highest AWM of 4.11 interpreted as Serious. On the other hand, the indicator “Lack of interest of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* to conduct *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan* about the bad effects of illegal fishing” obtained the lowest AWM of 2.50 interpreted as Less Serious.

5.1.2.2. The area of Application of Human Resources had an AWM of 2.77. interpreted as Moderately Serious. The indicator “Insufficient knowledge of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* in the conduct of Boarding Procedure” obtained the highest AWM of 3.30 and was interpreted as Serious. On the other hand, the indicator “Lack of Maritime Police personnel and *Bantay Dagat* deployed in the coastal areas” obtained the lowest AWM of 2.52 interpreted as Moderately Serious.

5.1.2.3. The area of Coordinative Activities had an overall mean of 2.28 and was interpreted as Moderately Serious. The indicator “Delay in rendering report of illegal fishing activities by the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* due to inadequacy of communication device” obtained the highest AWM of 2.54 interpreted as Moderately Serious. On the other hand, the indicator “Lack of coordination between the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* in the information with other law enforcement agencies” obtained the lowest AWM of 2.14 interpreted as Less Serious.

5.1.3. All respondent groups have indicated various degrees of seriousness for the recommended solutions to the problems encountered by the partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* in three areas.

5.1.3.1. The area of Innovative Approach had an OWM of 3.98 and was interpreted as Recommended. The indicator “Monthly conduct of *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan* to serve as community awareness on the bad effects of illegal fishing” obtained the highest AWM of 4.20 interpreted as Highly Recommended. On the other hand, the indicator “Installation of buoy marker on the marine protected areas to determine the focus of seaborne patrol operation” obtained the lowest AWM of 3.85 interpreted as Recommended.

5.1.3.2. The area of Application of Human Resources had an OWM of 4.15 interpreted as Recommended. The indicator “Actual demonstration of Boarding Procedure during the conduct of training for the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat*” obtained the highest AWM of 4.39 interpreted as Highly Recommended. On the other hand, the indicator “Orient the LGU on the free legal assistance program” obtained the lowest AWM of 3.69 interpreted as Recommended.

5.1.3.3. The area of Coordinative Activities had an OWM of 4.12 and was interpreted as Recommended. The indicator, “PNP to provide cellphones to the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* in coordination with the SMART in connection with OPLAN DALOY program” had a mean of 4.44 and was interpreted as Highly Recommended. On the other hand, the indicator “Conduct lecture on the Arrest, Search, and Seizure to the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* to avoid the bungling of the case” obtained the lowest AWM of 3.63 interpreted as Recommended.

5.1.4. The results of the interviews conducted all pointed to the positive assessment and acceptance of the partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* against the campaign against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay. Moreover, all sectors that provided qualitative data underscored the need to enhance the partnership to ensure work efficiency. Financial and logistical supports were major considerations that must be balanced with efficient and appropriate training.

Conclusions

From the findings of the study discussed in the previous sections, the following conclusions are drawn;

1. The partnership of the Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* in Balayan Bay is evident and therefore felt and valued by various sectors of the communities. The enhancement and improvement of the coordinated response against illegal fishing also show visible results, particularly in the area of “Innovative Approach” and “Application of Human Resources,” the variables which were rated and the lowest by the group of respondents consequent to indicators “Formulate and conduct Coastal Law Enforcement Training for Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat*.”

2. The most pressing problems encountered affecting the complex serious problems encountered relative to the partnership of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* are the areas of “Innovative Approach” and “Application of Human Resources” Both are given the highest ratings by the respondents which have enumerated the following corresponding indicators to wit; “Failure of the PNP to formulate and conduct Coastal Law Enforcement Training to the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* due to the non-inclusion to the Annual Training Program” and “Insufficient knowledge of the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* in the conduct of Boarding Procedure.”

3. Based on the survey, the enhancement of the partnership between the Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat* in Balayan Bay is through the conduct of training which is a highly recommended measure to improve law enforcement operations. Standing out among the indicators are the following;” Monthly conduct of *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan* to serve as community awareness on the bad effects of illegal fishing” and “Conduct of quarterly Coastal Law Enforcement Training to Maritime Police, and *Bantay Dagat*”

4. A regular conduct of Monthly or Quarterly *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan* with the participation of community residents to be presided over by the representatives of the Maritime Group, and *Bantay Dagat* was also on the priority list among the groups of the respondent. This activity aims to inform the community of the bad effects of illegal fishing, the status of the thrusts of the PNP Maritime Group against illegal fishing, and encourage the stakeholders to provide suggestions, inputs, and material support that will serve as additional resource generation for its effective implementation.

Recommendations

In consideration of the study's findings, the following recommendations are advanced:

1. The Maritime Police and *Bantay Dagat* partnership must continue as a matter of concerted efforts and increased involvement of the community that has the greatest stake to attain a safe maritime environment, sustainable fish harvest, and improved police-community partnership. Other involved sector like BFAR, LGU, NGO, FARMC and local fisherfolks must continue to show the value and importance of partnership through a regular monthly/quarterly *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan*.
2. During the conduct of *Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan*, topics on sustainable fishery management introduced by USAID program to stop illegal fishing must be discussed such as; a) Ecosystems Improved for Sustainable Fisheries (ECOFISH 2012-2017), a program which assist the Government of the Philippines, local governments, the private sector and stakeholders to strengthen fisheries governance, management and enforcement; b) National Stock Assessment Program (2015) which provide technical assistance to improve and standardize the program training curriculum, train new Philippine Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources field personnel on data collection in more than 250 sites and enhance the Bureau's competencies to analyze the exploitation statuses of economically important fisheries; c) National Oceanic Atmospheric Administration (NOAA 2014-2017) Philippine Support Program, which assist the BFAR to improve its vessel monitoring system and conducts training to fishery law enforcement agencies in setting up and analyzing information on an Alert System for Boat Detection for municipal waters and seasonal closure of critical fisheries; d) Philippines Biodiversity Program, which provides technical support to the task forces and interagency law enforcement

groups to improve coordination across agencies and facilitate the investigation and prosecution of environmental crimes including those related to IUU fishing and; e) Protect Wildlife (2016-2021), This new activity aims to conserve biodiversity in key protected areas in the Philippines and demonstrate the integration of conservation and development outcomes. The activity will achieve these dual objectives using a systems approach that involves capacity building and technical assistance, conservation finance and partnerships, behavior change, science and technology and environmental law enforcement; f) Rest the Bay (2014), a program which Implemented the closed season to address economic losses for fishers, raising awareness of the importance of the closed season, and ensuring enforcement.

3. The increasing value of fishery law enforcement must be stressed by the partnership, and this can be only achieved if the expected outputs are balanced by the required training that must be conducted. Formulation of Coastal Law Enforcement Training (CLET) must be done which will be the basis of the conduct of periodic training.

4. Communication is an indispensable pre-requisite. To achieve this, open communication lines must be guaranteed with all communication devices in order as specified in the OPLAN DALOY under the Ecosystem Improved for Sustainable Fishery (ECOFISH) program of the USAID to act immediately on the reported illegal fishing activities.

5. After the conduct of training, the creation of Fishery Law Enforcement Team (FLET) composes of Maritime Police, and Bantay Dagat must be created that will serve as a quick response team on the reported illegal fishing activities in the area.

6. Basic Intelligence subjects must be included in the POI and participants

from the intelligence community must be invited to attend to maintain a close intelligence network among the law enforcer and the community for the reporting system on the intrusion of fishing vessels from nearby provinces of Batangas.

7. Policy recommendation on the creation of Municipal Fishery Council in every municipality within the Balayan Bay composed of representatives from LGU, PNP Maritime Group, BFAR-FARMC, PCG and other concern stakeholders to discuss the proposal of USAID on the livelihood programs of USAID measures to stop illegal fishing.

XI. REFERENCES

- Arase, S.E., Iheanyi P.O. & Iwuofor, I.P. (2007). *Policing Nigeria in the 21st century*. Spectrum Books Ltd., Ibadan.
- Bantay Dagat. [www.psdu.org/sdvillage.ph/coastal/bantay dagat htm](http://www.psdu.org/sdvillage.ph/coastal/bantay_dagat.htm)
- Boba, R., Weisburd, D., & Meeker, J.W. (2009). *The limits of regional data sharing and regional problem solving: Observation from the East Valley.CA COMPASS Initiative*. Volume: 12 Issue: Pages: 22-41
- Calderon J.F. & Gonzales E.C. (2014). *Methods of Research and Thesis Writing*. National Bookstore
- Calvan, D.F. (2017). *End Illegal Fishing, Duterte Urged*.Oceana. <https://ph.oceana.org/press-releases/end-illegal-fishing-duterte-urged/>
- Chappel, A.T., (2009). *The Philosophical Versus the Actual Adoption of Community Policing*. Criminal Justice Review Volume: 34 Issue 1: Pages: 5- 28
- Costanza, E.E., Helins R., Ratansi, S.; Kilburn Jr., JC. & Harman, JE (2010). *Boom to bust or bust to boom? Following the effects of Weed and Seed zoning in New Britain*. Connecticut from 1995-2000, Police Quarterly pp. 49- 72.
- Department of Environment and Natural Resources, Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources of Department of Agriculture, and Department of Interior and Local Government Philippine (2001). *Coastal Management Guidebook series on Coastal Law Enforcement*. Project of the Department of the Department of Environmental and Natural Resources, Cebu City, Philippines. Page 58
- Domingo, R. W. (2017). *Government forms task force vs illegal fishing*. Philippine Daily Inquirer. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/806912/govt-forms-task-force-vs-illegal-fishing#>
- Effanibi, E.O, Alemika E.E & Chukwuma, I.C. (2011). *Informal Policing Project: The CLEEN Foundation Report*. Justice Sector Platform- Nigeria.
- Gilbert, M.J., & Settles, T.L. (2007). *The next step: Indigenous development of neighborhood restorative community justice*. Criminal Justice Review pp.5-25.
- Guieb, R.; Green, G. & Armada, N. (2010). *Turning to Science to Build Consensus: The Seasonal Fishing Closure in Balayan Bay, Philippines*. USAID Biodiversity Integration Case Studies.
- Hickman, M.S., & Reaves B.A. (2001). *Community Policing in Local Police Department*. Justice Statistics Clearinghouse.
- Hills, A. (2011). *The dialectic of police reform in Nigeria*. The Journal of Modern African Studies, 46(2), 215-234. doi:10.1017/S0022278X08003200

- Inyang J.D., & Abraham L.E (2013). *Policing Nigeria: A case for a partnership between formal and informal police institutions*. Corpus ID: 55715914. issat.dcaf.ch.
- Inyang J.D., & Brown A.S (2011). *Community Police and Policing Problem: The Nigerian Situation*. International Journal of African Culture, Politics and Development, Politics, and Development volume 6, pp. 1-12.
- Magsombol.J.C. (2021). *Batangas gathers 433 Bantay Dagat volunteers*. Journal News Online. <https://journalnews.com.ph/batangas-gathers-433-bantay-dagat-volunteers/>
- Mazerole, L., Wickes R., & McBroom (2010). *Community Variations in Violence: The role of social ties and collective efficacy in comparative context*. Journal of research in crime and delinquency_ Pages 3-30.
- Moore, M.H., Trojanowics, R.C., & Kelling G.L. (2008). *Crime and Policing*. Eaglewood Cliffs NS Printing Hall Press.
- Morabito, M.S. (2010). *Understanding Policing as an Innovation: Patterns of Adoption, Crime, and Delinquency*. SAGE Publications.
- Oceana. (2020). *Stop Illegal Commercial Fishing in Municipal Waters*. <https://ph.oceana.org/our-campaigns/stop-illegal-commercial-fishing/>
- Ogadimma C. A. (2010). *Developing Country Studies*. www.iiste.org ISSN 2224-607X (Paper) ISSN 2225-0565. Vol.3, No.4,
- Palmiotto, M.J., Birzer, M.L, & Unnithan P.N (2000). *Training in Community Policing: A Suggested Curriculum Policing: An international journal of police strategies & management*. Volume 23. Issue 1. Pages 8-21
- Philippine Constitution (1987).
- Philippine National Police (PNP) Letter of Instruction (LOI) 22/69 (Barangay Peacekeeping Operation)
- PNP LOI 30/20 (PNP Organizational Plan” SAMBAYAN 2002).
- PNP Manual (2009). Barangay Peacekeeping Operation and Barangay Peacekeeping Action Team (BPAT).
- Pryjomico R. (2011). *Partnership for Security: The Citizen’s Police Liaison Committee in Karachi, Pakistan*. Humanitarian Exchange Magazine issue no. 50. Page 3
- Republic Act 7160 (The Local Government Code).
- Republic Act 10654. (2015). An Act to Prevent, Deter, and Eliminate Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated Fishing; Amending Republic Act 8550 otherwise

known as “The Philippine Fisheries Code of 1998” And for other purposes.

Rosenbaum, D.P. (2003). Evaluating Multi-Agency, Anti-Crime Partnership: Theory Design and Measurement Issues: *Crime Prevention Studies* Volume 14 pp. 171-225.

Rosenbaum, D.P., Graziano, L.M., Stephens, C.D., & Schuck, A.M. (2011). *Understanding Community Policing and Legitimacy-Seeking Behavior Virtual Reality*. *Police Quarterly* Volume: 14 Issue: 1 Pages: 25-47

Skogan, W.G., Steiner, L., DuBois, J., Gudell, J.E., & Fagan, A. (2002). *Community Policing and the New Immigrants: Latino in Chicago*. US Department of Justice Program. U.S. Programs National Institute of Justice 189908. Pages 1-29.

Skolnick, J.H., Bayley, D.H. (2013) *Community Policing: Issues and Practices Around the World*. NCJ Number 111428.

Tilley, N. (2008). *The Development of Community Policing in England: Networks, Knowledge and Neighbourhoods*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470773215.ch4>

Trojanowicz, R.C., & Kelling, G.L. (1988). “Crime and Policing.” *Perspectives on Policing*. Copy at <https://tinyurl.com/ydcl8268>

Wehrman, M.M., De Angelis, J. (2011). *Citizen’s willingness to participate in police-community partnership: Exploring the influence of race and neighborhood context*. *Police Journal* pp.48-69.

Wells, W., Schafer, J.A., Verano, S.P., & Bynum, T.S. (2006). *Neighborhood residents’ production of order: The effects of collective efficacy on responses to neighborhood problems*. *Crime and Delinquency*. Pages 523- 550.

Wilson, R.F. (2009). *Why Neighborhood Matters? : The Importance of Geographic Composition*. *Geography & Public Safety*. Pages 1-20.

Yero, A. J., Othman, B., Abu, S., Jeffrey L. D’Silva, A.H. & Sulaiman. (2012). *Re-visiting concept and theories of community policing*. *International Journal of Academic Research Part B*; 4(4), 51-55

USAID. (2020). *Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated Fishing in the Philippines*. <https://biodiversitylinks.org/projects/mission-projects/illegal-unreported-and-unregulated-policy-milestones>

US Department of Justice, Office of Justice Program. (2010). *Community Policing*. Retrieved from Bureau of Justice Statistics. <http://bjj.ojp.usdoj.gov/index.cf>

Wikipedia. *Map of Balayan Bay*. October 1, 2022.

Yan, G. (2018, March). *End Illegal Fishing, Duterte Urged*. Oceana. <https://ph.oceana.org/press-releases/end-illegal-fishing-duterte-urged/>

Appendix 1

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Part I. Respondents' assessment of the partnership of the Maritime Police and Bantay Dagat against blast fishing at Balayan Bay. (*Pagtaya ng mga sumasagot sa samahan ng Maritime Police at Bantay Dagat sa pagsugpo ng illegal na pangingsda sa Balayan Bay*)

Direction: Please state your assessment of the partnership of Maritime Police and Bantay Dagat against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay. Kindly indicate your answer by placing a check (/) mark in the appropriate box using the following scale below. (*Sagutin ang inyong pagtaya kung nakikita ang samahan ng Maritime Police at Bantay Dagat sa pagsugpo ng illegal na pangingsda sa Balayan Bay) sa pamamagitan ng paglalagay ng (/) sa kaukulang espasyo sa ibaba.*

5- Very Evident (*Laging Nakikita*) (VE) 4- Evident (*Nakikita*)

(E) 3- Moderately Evident (*Medyo Nakikita*) (ME)

2- Less Evident (*Hindi Gaanong Nakikita*) (LE) 1-Not Evident (*Hindi Nakikita*)

(NE)

Innovative Approaches (*Makabagong Pamamaraan*)

INDICATORS	5 (VE)	4 (E)	3 (ME)	2 (LE)	1 (NE)
1. Inform the community about the fishery law enforcement program and the bad effects of illegal fishing. (<i>Ipinapabatid sa pamayanan ang masamang epekto ng ilegal na pangingsda</i>).					
2. Provide an awareness campaign of the Adopt a Marine Protected Area Program to determine the focus of seaborne patrol operations. (<i>Nagkakaloob ng kamalayan sa kampanya para protektahan ang Marine Protected Areas upang malaman kung saan tututukan ang patrolya sa dagat</i>).					
3. Formulate and conduct Coastal					

Law Enforcement Training for Police and Bantay Dagat. (<i>Nagpapanukala at nangangagasiwa ng Coastal Law Enforcement Training para sa mga Pulis at Bantay Daga</i>)t.					
4. Work hand in hand with LGUs and NGOs in the campaign against illegal fishing. (<i>Nakikipagkaisa sa mga LGU at NGO sa kampanya laban sa ilegal na pangingsda</i>).					
5. Conduct seaborne patrol operations in the coastal areas of Balayan Bay. (<i>Nagsasagawa ng patrolya sa baybaying dagat ng Balayan</i>).					

Application of Human Resources (*Paggamit ng Yamang-tao*)

INDICATORS	5 (VE)	4 (E)	3 (ME)	2 (LE)	1 (NE)
1 Exercise proper execution of the Boarding Procedure by the Police and Bantay Dagat personnel. (<i>Gumagamit ng tamang pamamaraan ng pagpapatupad ng batas sa pangingsda lulan ng sasakyang pandagat ng mga pulis at Bantay Dagat</i>).					
2. Employ additional police personnel and recruitment of Bantay Dagat with corresponding office orders. (<i>Nagpapadala ng karagdagang mga pulis at Bantay Dagat sa paglaban sa ilegal na pangingsda</i>).					
3. Show awareness by the PNP and LGU of seaborne patrol equipment communication devices for the police and Bantay Dagat. (<i>Ipinapakita ang kamalayan ng mga pulis at Bantay Dagat sa paggamit ng mga komunikasyon sa pagpatrolya sa dagat</i>).					
4. Activate free legal assistance to the LGU to uplift their morale and welfare. (<i>Pinalakas ang libheng tulong legal ng LGU para itaas ang moral ng mga pulis at Bantay Dagat</i>).					
5. Utilize available gas allocation and financial assistance as planned. (<i>May</i>					

<i>nakalaan na tulong para sa gasolina at pinansyal sa pagpapatupad ng batas).</i>					
--	--	--	--	--	--

Coordinative Activities (*Magkasamang Magpatupad*)

INDICATORS	5 (VE)	4 (E)	3 (ME)	2 (LE)	1 (NE)
The Maritime Police and Bantay Dagat					
1. Act on a report based on surveillance of illegal fishing activities (<i>Agarang pagkilos sa mga ulat ng pagmamatyag ng ilegal na pangangisda</i>).					
2. Enforce existing fishery laws/ordinances against illegal fishing in the coastal areas without fear or favor. <i>(Ipinapatupad ang mga umiiral na batas at ordinansa laban sa ilegal na pangangisda ng walang takot at kinikilingan)</i> .					
3. Execute joint affidavit of apprehension and file case against violators of fishery laws/ordinances. <i>(Isinasagawa ang magkasamang salaysay ng paghuli sa lumalabag sa mga batas at ordinansa sa pangangisda)</i> .					
4 . Maintain close coordination with the municipal/city government by attending Peace and Order Council Meetings about fishery law enforcement. <i>(Pinapanatili ang pakikipagtulungan sa mga pamahalaang bayan at lunsod sa pamagitan ng pagdalo ng Peace and Order Council tungkol sa pagpapatupad ng batas pangangisda)</i> .					
5. Coordinate with other law enforcement agencies through information networking system about illegal fishing . <i>(Pakikipagtulungan sa ibat-ibang sangay ng pamahalaan ng nagpapatupad ng batas para sa pagpapalaganap ng inpormasyon laban sa ilegal na pangangisda)</i> .					

PART II. Problems encountered by the partnership of the Maritime Police and Bantay against illegal fishing in Balayan Bay.(Problemang Hinaharap ng Samahan ng Maritime Police at Bantay Dagat pagsugpo sa pagsugpo ng illegal na pangingsda sa BalayanBay

Direction: Please state your assessment of the problems encountered by the partnership encountered by the Maritime Police and Bantay Dagat against blast fishing at Balayan Bay. Kindly indicate your answer by placing (/) mark in the appropriate box using the following scale below. .(Sagutin ang inyong pagtaya kung nakikita ang samahan ng Maritime Police at Bantay Dagat sa pagsugpo ng illegal na pangingsda sa Balayan Bay) sa pamamagitan ng paglalagay ng (/) sa kaukulang espasyo sa ibaba).

5- Very Serious (*Masyadong Seryoso*) (VS) 4- Serious (*Seryoso*)
 (S) 3- Moderately Serious (*Medyo Seryoso*) (MS) 2- Less Serious (*Hindi Gaanong Seryoso*) (LS) 1- Not Serious (*Hindi Seryoso*)
 (NS)

Innovative Approaches (*Makabagong Pamamaraan*)

INDICATORS	5 (VS)	4 (S)	3 (MS)	2 (LS)	1 (NS)
1. Lack of interest of the police and Bantay Dagat to conduct Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan to the community about the bad effects of ilegal fishing.(<i>Kulang sa interes ang mga pulis at Bantay Dagat para maglunsad ng Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan sa mga pamayanan tungkol sa masamang epekto ng ilegal na pangingsda</i>).					
2. Unable to identify the Marine Protected Areas by the police and Bantay Dagat to determine the focus of their seaborne patrol operations.(<i>Walang kakayahan malaman ang mga Marine Protected Areas ang mga Pulis at Bantay Dagat para doon nila palakasin ang patrolya sa dagat</i>).					
3. Failure of the PNP to formulate and					

conduct Coastal Law Enforcement Training for the Police and Bantay Dagat (<i>Kabiguan ng PNP na ipatupad ang "Coastal Law Enforcement Training" para sa mga pulis at Bantay Dagat</i>).					
4. Lack of commitment by the PNP and LGU to give awards and commendations to Police and Bantay Dagat who exhibit dedication to service. (<i>Kulang ng pagkilala ng PNP at LGU na magbigay ng parangal sa mga pulis at Bantay Dagat na nagapapatupad ng batas pangingsda</i>).					
5. Irregular conduct of joint seaborne patrol operations due to the absence of the Fishery Law Enforcement Team. (<i>Iregular na magkasamang pagpapatrolya sa dagat dahil sa kawalan ng "Fishery Law Enforcement Team"</i>).					

Application of Human Resources (*Paggamit ng Yamang-tao*)

INDICATORS	5 (VS)	4 (S)	3 (MS)	2 (LS)	1 (NS)
1. Insufficient knowledge of the police and Bantay Dagat in the conduct of the Boarding Procedure. (<i>Kakulangan ng kaalaman ng mga pulis at Bantay Dagat sa pagsasagawa ng "Boarding Procedure"</i>).					
2 . Lack of police personnel and Bantay Dagat deployed in the coastal areas. (<i>Kakulangan ng mga pulis at Bantay Dagat na ilalagay sa mga baybaying dagat</i>).					
3. Failure by the PNP and LGU to provide additional seaborne patrol equipment and communication device. (<i>Kabiguan ng PNP at LGU na maglaan ng karagdagang gamit sa pagpapatrolyas sa dagat at komunikasyon</i>).					
4.No legal assistance was provided by the PNP and LGU to the police and Bantay Dagat. (<i>Walang tulong legal na</i>					

<i>ipinapagkaloob ng PNP at LGU sa mga pulis at Bantay Dagat).</i>					
5. Limited gas allocation provided by the PNP and LGU to police and Bantay Dagat. <i>(Limitado ang ibinibigay na panggasolina sa mga patrol boat ng LGU sa mga pulis at Bantay Dagat).</i>					

Coordinative Activities (*Magkasamang Magpatupad*)

INDICATORS	5 (VS)	4 (S)	3 (MS)	2 (LS)	1 (NS)
1. Delay in rendering reports of illegal fishing activities by the police and Bantay Dagat due to inadequacy of communication devices. <i>-(Naaantala ang pagbibigay ng report sa illegal na pangangisda ng mga pulis at Bantay Dagat dahil sa kakulangan ng gamit sa komunikasyon.</i>					
2. Unwillingness of the police and Bantay Dagat to enforce fishery laws/ordinances due to lack of commitment and dedication. Tagalog- <i>(Ayaw ng mga pulis at Bantay Dagat na magpatupad ng batas at ordinansa sa pangangisda dahil sa lakulangan ng dedikasyon).</i>					
3. Lack of interest by the police and Bantay Dagat to file cases due to fear of counter-charge against them. <i>(Kulang ang interes ng mga pulis at Bantay Dagat ng magsampa ng kaso dahil sa pangamba na baka sila ay makasuhan din).</i>					
4. Uncooperative attitude of the police and Bantay Dagat to support the anti-illegal fishing program of the city/municipal government, BFAR and NGO. <i>(Ayaw makipagtulunagn ng mga pulis at Bantay Dagat para suportahan ang programa ng mga Bayan at Syudad sa pagsugpo ng illegal na paningingisda).</i>					
5. Lack of coordination between the police and Bantay Dagat in the information networking with other law enforcement agencies. <i>(Kulang sa</i>					

<i>koordinasyon ang mga pulis at Bantay Dagat sa mga inpormasyon sa ibat ibang sangay ng nagpapapatupad ng batas).</i>					
--	--	--	--	--	--

PART III. The proposed solution to address the problems encountered by the partnership of the Maritime Police and Bantay Dagat against illegal fishing at Balayan Bay. (Solusyon para matugunan ang problemang kinakaharap ng Maritime Police at Bantay Dagat sa pagsugpo ng illegal na pangingsda sa Balayan Bay.

Direction: Please state your assessment of the measures that can be proposed to address the problems encountered by the partnership of the Maritime Police and Bantay Dagat against blast fishing. Kindly indicate your answer by placing a check (/) mark in the appropriate box using the following scale below. *.(Sagutin ang inyong pagtaya kung nakikita ang samahan ng Maritime Police at Bantay Dagat sa pagsugpo ng illegal na pangingsda sa Balayan Bay) sa pamamagitan ng paglalagay ng (/) sa kaukulang espasyo sa ibaba).*

- 5- Highly Recommended (*Higit na Ipinapanukala*) (HR) 4-
- Recommended (*Ipinapanukala*) (R)
- 3- Moderately Recommended (*Medyo Ipinapanukala*) (MR)
- 2- Less Recommended (*Hindi Gaanong Ipinapanukala*) (LR) 1-Not
- Recommended (*Hindi Ipinapanukala*) (NR)

Innovative Approach (*Makabagong Pamamaraan*)

INDICATORS	5 (HR)	4 (R)	3 (MR)	2 (LR)	1 (NR)
1. Monthly conduct of Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan to serve as community awareness on the bad effects of illegal fishing. (<i>Buwanang pagpapasagawa ng Pulong pulong/Ugnayan para ipaalam sa pamayanan ang masamang dulot ng illegal na pangingsda).</i>					
2. Installation of buoy marker on the Marine Protected Areas to determine the focus of seaborne patrol operation. (<i>Paglalagay ng mga palatandaan ng</i>					

mga boya sa mga Marine Protected Areas para malaman ang pokus ng pagpapatrolya).					
3. Conduct quarterly Coastal Law Enforcement Training to police and Bantay Dagat.(Pagsasagawa ng “Coastal Law Enforcenment Course para sa mga pulis at Bantay Dagat tuwing ikatlong buwan).					
4. Giving awards and recognition by the PNP and LGU to police and Bantay Dagat during special occasions for exemplary service.(Pagbibigay ng parangal at pagkilala sa mga pulis at Bantay Dagat para sa kanilang tapat na pagtupad ng kanilang tungkulin).					
5. Creation of a Fishery Law Enforcement Team composed of police and Bantay Dagat that provides lectures on fishery laws.(Paglulunsad ng Fishery law Enforcement Team na binubuo ng mga pulis at Bantay Dagat).					

Application of Human Resources- (Paggamit ng Yamang-tao)

INDICATORS	5 (HR)	4 (R)	3 (MR)	2 (LR)	1 (NR)
1. Actual demonstration of Boarding Procedure during the conduct of training for the police and Bantay Dagat. (Aktuwal na pagpapakita ng Boarding Procedure sa pagsasanay ng mga pulis at Bantay Dagat)					
2. Conduct a series of meetings on the disadvantages of illegal fishing in the community.(Pagsasagawa ng mga pagpupulong sa mga pinsala na dulot ng ilegal na pangingsda sa pamayanan.)					
3. Conduct training to the PNP and Bantay Dagat on the proper handling of the issued seaborne patrol equipment and communication device. (Pagsasagawa ng pagsasasanay sa mga pulis at Bantay Dagat sa tamang paggamit ng gamit sa patrolya at komunikasyon)					
4. Orient the LGU on the free legal assistance program.(Ipaalam sa LGU ang libreng tulong legal para sa mga pulis at Bantay Dagat).					
5. Creation of Technical Working Group composed of representatives from PNP, LGU,					

and NGO and discuss the status of logistical support the program. (<i>Pagtatag ng Technical Working Group mula sa PNP, LGU, at NGO para pag-usapan ang kalagayan ng kagamitan sa pagpapatupad ng batas sa pangangisda</i>)					
--	--	--	--	--	--

Coordinative Activities (*Magkasamang Magpatupad*)

INDICATORS	5 (HR)	4 (R)	3 (MR)	2 (LR)	1 (NR)
1. PNP to provide cell phones to the police and Bantay Dagat in coordination with the LGUs and NGOs. (<i>Pagbibigay ng PNP ng mga cellphones sa mga pulis at Bantay Dagat sa tulong ng LGU at NGO para magamit sa komunikasyon</i>).					
2. Conduct a lecture on the Rules on Criminal Procedure and Rules of Engagement to the police and Bantay Dagat. (<i>Pagsasagawa ng pagsasanay sa Rules on Criminal Procedures at Rules of Engagement sa mga Pulis at Bantay dagat</i>).					
3. Conduct of lecture on Arrest, Search, and Seizure to police and Bantay Dagat to avoid the bungling of the case. (<i>Pagsasagawa ng pagsasanay ng Arrest, Search, and Seizure sa mga pulis at Bantay Dagat para maiwasan ang pagkatalo ng mga kaso sa korte</i>).					
4. Include in the Pulong-pulong/Ugnayan about the fishery law enforcement program of the PNP, LGU and BFAR. (Isama sa Pulong/pulong/Ugnayan ang tungkol sa pagpapatupad ng batas pangangisda).					
5. Conduct a seminar on basic intelligence and invite other law enforcement intelligence communities. (<i>Pagsasagawa ng seminar sa basic intelligence at anyayaha ang ibang sanagay sa pagpapatupad ng batas pangangisda</i>).					

Appendix 2

Pictorial with Dr. Rogelio Demelletes, Chief of DENR Law Enforcement Division, and Bantay Dagat Coordinator

Consulted Dr. Rogelio Demelletes, DENR Chief, Law Enforcement Office and Bantay Dagat Coordinator in drafting survey questionnaires and status of Bantay Dagat in Region 4A particularly in the province of Batangas.

Appendix 3

Pictorial with PCol Greg Togonon, Chief of Regional Maritime Unit 4A.

Interview with Police Colonel Greg R. Togonon through Zoom Meeting discussing the accomplishment of the Regional Maritime Unit 4A on the campaign against illegal fishing highlighting on the joint operation with the Bantay Dagat.

Appendix 4

Pictorial with PCapt Benito Siddayao, Chief of Batangas Maritime Police

Interview with Police Captain Benito Siddayao Jr. discussing the accomplishment of the Batangas Police Station on the campaign against illegal fishing highlighting on the joint operation with the Bantay Dagat at Balayan Bay.

Appendix 5

Pictorial with Engineer Ian Manalo, Professor, and Statistician of Quezon City University.

Consultation meeting with Engr. Ian Manalo, professor and statistician of Quezon City University about the statistical computation of raw data based on gathered survey questionnaires from the respondents.

Appendix 6

Pictorial During Distribution of Survey Questionnaires to Batangas Maritime Police.

Meeting with Maritime Police stationed at Lemery, Batangas discussing the details of survey questionnaires and distribution to respondents.

Appendix 7

Pictorial During Distribution of Survey Questionnaires to Bantay Dagat of Lemery Batangas

During distribution of survey questionnaires to the Bantay Dagat of Lemery, Batangas with the assistance of Batangas Maritime Police.

Appendix 8

Pictorial During the Distribution of Survey Questionnaires with the residents of coastal barangays at Mabini, Batangas.

Picture taking before the distribution of Survey Questionnaires with the residents of coastal barangays at Mabini, Batangas showing Balayan Bay at the background.

Appendix 9

Pictorial During the Distribution of Survey Questionnaires with the residents of coastal barangays at Balayan, Batangas.

During the Distribution of Survey Questionnaires with the residents of coastal barangays at Balayan, Batangas with the assistance of Maritime Police.

Appendix 10

Pictorial During the Distribution of Survey Questionnaires with the residents of coastal barangays at Balayan, Batangas.

During the Distribution of Survey Questionnaires with the residents of coastal barangays at San Luis, Batangas with the assistance of Maritime Police.

Appendix 11

Pictorial during meeting with representatives from BFAR, FARMC, and Bantay Dagat to discuss their present strategy against illegal fishing.

